

D2.2 Guidelines for public engagement and dialogue

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Executive summary

The present deliverable is included in the frame of the Work Package 2 of GENESIS project (Geologically Enhanced Nature-Based Solutions for climate change resiliency of critical water InfraStructure), whose overarching aim is to strengthen social support for the adoption of Nature-Based Solutions. This deliverable presents social engagement approaches and participatory methodologies, which emerge as the most effective considering the features of the different sites in the Macaronesian context. The methodological approach followed is presented at first to inform the reader on the main resources used to draft the text, the selection done among them and the steps taken in the analysis and drafting process. Secondly, the authors explain the criteria and dimensions deemed relevant to be used in the Macaronesian pilots to identify the best civic participatory methods. Both the criteria and the dimensions were identified on the basis of the previous Task 2.1 and Deliverable 2.1., and on the lessons-learnt from the project development and on-site activities performed until the time of writing. The final selected methods are then presented and comparatively assessed to provide an overview of their characteristics. In the following chapter, a similar presentation is done for the GENESIS pilot sites. After having clarified both the methods and the pilots taken into consideration, a matching exercise with graphic tables is performed to indicate which methods best fit which GENESIS site. To provide hands-on knowledge, the two participatory activities performed in Madeira and La Palma are reported, together with challenges experienced and the lessons-learnt. Some final conclusions mark the end of the deliverable.

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Annexes

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1 Introduction

Public engagement and dialogue constitute a central pillar of the GENESIS project, underpinning the social legitimacy and long-term sustainability of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) for water management in the Macaronesian region. In fact, the project relies upon Work Package (WP) 2 “NBS Mainstreaming and Social Engagement” to enhance mainstreaming of NBS and social support for their adoption in general and more specifically in the communities in the area of each demonstrator site. Within T2.2, ALDA is in charge of implementing community engagement activities on site and supporting the local, regional and European stakeholder engagement together with the support of some other GENESIS project partners (IST, UMa, CIAP, CAT, CMH, CANAR, UCV, ITC). This deliverable is drafted on the basis of the engagement activities implemented so far (month 18 from the project start), providing a document to reflect on the outcomes achieved and achievable. The aim of this deliverable is to provide guidance on how NBS can be promoted in the demonstrator sites based in the Canary Islands, Portugal, Cape Verde and Azores (La Palma, El Hierro, Gran Canaria, Faial, Madeira, Santiago) using different stakeholder and citizen engagement practices and methods in order to involve citizens in the co-design of solutions that safeguard freshwater using deliberative dialogues; to design, test and validate new water governance models; and to engage and educate local communities about groundwater management through citizen science.

As part of Work Package 2, this deliverable builds upon the outcomes of Task 2.1 (*D2.1 GENESIS Water Governance Framework of social acceptability*), translating its analytical and empirical findings into practical guidelines for inclusive stakeholder participation, targeted for each demonstrator. More specifically, D2.1 provided a comprehensive assessment of the water governance landscape and the social acceptability of NBS across the GENESIS pilot sites, combining stakeholder mapping, surveys, and semi-structured interviews. The analysis explored institutional arrangements, decision-making processes, levels of stakeholder awareness and trust, and perceived barriers and enablers for the adoption of Nature-Based Solutions. Particular attention was given to the roles of public authorities, water managers, civil society organisations, and citizens, as well as to the socio-cultural specificities influencing participation and governance effectiveness in each island context. Building on this evidence base, the present deliverable does not replicate the analytical assessment of governance structures. Rather, it complements D2.1 and operationalises its key findings by identifying appropriate public engagement and dialogue approaches. In line with established frameworks on public participation in environmental decision-making, this document recognises that participation can take different forms - from information provision and consultation to active involvement and co-decision - each associated with varying degrees of influence, inclusiveness, and deliberative quality. The activities of Task 2.1 and those described in this deliverable show that Macaronesian archipelagos - Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, and Cape Verde - face converging water challenges shaped by climatic variability, demographic pressures, and institutional fragmentation. Such activities confirm a high level of social acceptance for NBS across all regions and reveal systemic barriers to their implementation, including limited technical capacity, weak inter-agency coordination, and inadequate public participation mechanisms. Consequently, strengthening dialogue and engagement between experts, policymakers, and citizens becomes essential to bridge the gap between conceptual support and operational adoption.

Furthermore, research on environmental governance (Richardson and Razzaque 2005) highlights that well-designed participatory processes contribute not only to improved decision quality, but also to enhanced legitimacy, accountability, and long-term policy effectiveness. Participation processes that are transparent, inclusive, and deliberative can foster trust in institutions, reduce conflict, and increase the likelihood that adopted measures are socially robust and locally embedded. These considerations are particularly relevant in insular contexts, where social networks are dense, institutional capacities vary, and environmental vulnerabilities are highly visible in everyday life.

The present guidelines provide a framework for designing participatory engagement processes tailored to the socio-cultural and institutional contexts of each demonstrator site. They aim to operationalise inclusivity, transparency, and mutual learning in the co-creation of NBS, ensuring that diverse perspectives inform both design and decision-making processes. The deliverable thereby contributes directly to the development of comprehensive, site-specific public engagement and dialogue strategies to be implemented across the nine pilots of the GENESIS project. To achieve this objective, core participatory methods drawn from academic literature, international practice, and project-based experience have been screened and analysed. Their suitability has been assessed in relation to contextual enabling conditions, governance capacity and levels of public awareness.

In this way, Task 2.2 translates the diagnostic insights of D2.1 into actionable and context-sensitive guidance, supporting the co-creation and long-term governance of Nature-Based Solutions across the Macaronesian region.

2 Methodological framework

2.1 Conceptual approach

The methodological framework of this deliverable integrates evidence from the empirical research conducted in Task 2.1 and Task 2.2, the resources that ALDA has developed within its long-term experience in citizen engagement activities, together with other sources and established international standards for participatory governance. Specifically, it embeds qualitative data from stakeholder surveys and semi-structured interviews performed under Task 2.1, focusing in particular on levels of awareness, trust, and perceived barriers to NBS implementation across islands. The full results are reported in D2.1 *GENESIS Water Governance Framework of social acceptability*. In addition, it incorporates ALDA's publications on citizens and stakeholders engagement for enhanced democratic participation, comprehension and promotion of EU values, digitalisation for inclusion and better democratic governance, environmental protection awareness and action (see all ALDA resources used in the References section) as well as best practices in public participation at global level, as compiled by Involve¹, which catalogues over seventy participatory and deliberative methods used internationally to engage citizens in decision-making processes; and complementary frameworks for participatory governance, notably the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) Spectrum of Participation (n.d.)², the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-Based Solutions (2020)³, the OECD Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions (2020)⁴ and the OECD Building Trust to Reinforce Democracy (2022)⁵.

The integration of these resources allows for a dual focus: (1) identifying the most effective methods for engaging diverse stakeholder groups in deliberative processes; and (2) aligning these methods with the specific social, institutional, and ecological characteristics of the Macaronesian pilot sites.

This document is aligned with Deliverable 7.2 - Ethics Guidelines, including GDPR, the ALLEA Code, and the gender dimension, as required by the Grant Agreement.

¹ Involve. *Methods*. Available at <https://www.involve.org.uk/resources/methods> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

² International Association of Public Participation (IAP2) n.d. <https://www.iap2.org/page/SpectrumEvolution> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

³ IUCN (2020). *Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS*. First edition. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

⁴ OECD (2020). *Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/339306da-en> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

⁵ OECD (2022). *Building Trust to Reinforce Democracy: Main Findings from the 2021 OECD Survey on Drivers of Trust in Public Institutions*, Building Trust in Public Institutions, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b407f99c-en> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

2.2 Selection criteria for the methods

Using a definition provided by the Institute for Development Studies, participatory methods mean “*ways of designing and implementing research and engagement which sit within a set of participatory values and principles. They include a range of activities with a common thread: enabling people to play an active and influential part in decisions which affect their lives*”⁶.

Out of the extensive pool of existing engagement methods and approaches, this deliverable deliberately focuses on those having features considered relevant and meaningful for the topic (water governance and NBS) and the context (Macaronesia islands) in which they would be applied. In particular, methods that could support different levels of participation as defined by the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) Spectrum were identified. The IAP2 Spectrum is a globally recognised framework defining five levels of public impact on decision-making: inform, consult, involve, collaborative, and empower. Such levels are defined by the IAP2⁷ as follows:

- *Inform: to provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions*
- *Consult: to obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions*
- *Involve: to work directly with the public throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered*
- *Collaborate: to partner with the public in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution*
- *Empower: to place final decision-making in the hands of the public*

In addition, as it will be better detailed in Chapter 5, the methods identified integrate different levels of economic and institutional capacity, and public awareness as defined in D2.1. The purpose of this differentiation is to fit different contexts - those of the pilots - presenting different features.

The following definitions of the three dimensions, deduced from the analysis conducted in D2.1, were used:

1. Economic capacity refers to the availability of financial resources and the broader economic conditions that determine whether Nature-based Solutions (NBS) can be implemented and sustained. It is closely associated with public budget constraints, access to dedicated financing mechanisms, and the ability to mobilise EU, national, or other funding sources. Although D2.1 consistently identifies financial and resource limitations as the most critical barrier across all four regions, slight differences can be identified among the different regions. Indeed, in the comparative framework (Table 8.1 of D2.1), economic capacity is differentiated by region (e.g. Moderate-High, Moderate, Low), reflecting variations in resource availability. Given that the different methodological approaches presented in Chapter 3 require differing financial resources, this must be taken into account.

⁶ Institute of Development Studies (IAP2) n.d. *What are participatory methods?* Available at: <https://www.participatorymethods.org/what-are-participatory-methods> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

⁷ International Association of Public Participation (IAP2), n.d., <https://www.iap2.org/page/SpectrumEvolution> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

2. Institutional capacity refers to the maturity, technical competence, and administrative ability of public institutions to design, coordinate, regulate, and implement NBS. It encompasses technical expertise, availability of trained professionals, existence of established water authorities, clarity of regulatory frameworks, and effectiveness of inter-agency coordination. In the cross-regional comparison provided by D2.1, institutional capacity is assessed in terms of governance maturity and operational strength, with regions characterised as having High, Moderate, or Low capacity depending on technical and organisational conditions. The level of institutional capacity of the different sites is considered a key element to assess the methods that suit them best based on their level of complexity. Methods considered to have a complex implementation process are more suitable for sites with high institutional capacity.
3. Public awareness can be described in terms of the level of familiarity, understanding, environmental consciousness, and social acceptability of NBS among citizens and stakeholders. It is also about trust in scientific actors, and strong environmental values, which provide a foundation for participatory governance approaches. In the comparative analysis conducted, public awareness is characterised using qualitative descriptors, indicating that this dimension captures both knowledge levels and environmental engagement. The existence of a high public awareness in a site would allow the application of more involving and empowering methods.

In addition, methods resulting in tangible outcomes such as shared visions, policy inputs, or local frameworks were preferred.

After selecting the relevant public engagement methods, the relative suitability of each method to the GENESIS pilots, depending on three specific dimensions identified and detailed in D2.1, was evaluated. As presented in Chapter 4 of this deliverable, GENESIS D2.1 provided a comparative assessment of the pilots across key dimensions relevant to NBS governance and implementation (see Table 8.1: *Comparative assessment of regional contexts for NBS implementation* of D2.1). Such dimensions included:

1. Economic Capacity
2. Institutional Capacity
3. Public Awareness
4. Governance Complexity
5. Primary Water Challenge
6. Cultural Compatibility
7. Financial Barrier Intensity
8. Priority NBS Types
9. Recommended Governance Model
10. Implementation Readiness

For the purposes of this deliverable, the eleven methods previously identified were matched with the GENESIS pilots mainly according to three of these dimensions which were considered more relevant, namely: 1. Economic Capacity, 2. Institutional Capacity and 3. Public Awareness.

To summarise, the following steps were taken:

1. Collecting and analysing public participatory methods from ALDA's repository and relevant online resources
2. Reviewing them to identify those relevant for water / NBS governance contexts
3. Match them with the GENESIS pilots cases, specifically following the analysis provided in D2.1 and prioritising the three dimensions of economic capacity, institutional capacity and public awareness, and taking into account the on-site activities done in the two events in Madeira and La Palma
4. Providing guidance on the best public engagement methods and relevant topics to consider in the contexts of the GENESIS pilots and similar, after performing the previous steps

Also, Chapter 6 provides the report of the two citizen engagement activities conducted in two of the project's sites.

Given the scope of the present deliverable, a more operative and less academic approach has been used in order to present the features of the identified participatory methods, allowing for a more hands-on use of the deliverable, better suited to the project's case studies.

This deliverable used AI assistance (GPT-5, OpenAI) as a supportive tool for data and information analysis and cross-check of the numerous resources on participatory methods available and reported in the References, and to summarize information from the D2.1. The AI system assisted under author supervision with systematisation of information and descriptive and multivariate analyses of data. All AI-assisted content underwent multi-step human review and editorial oversight by the document authors, who retain full responsibility for the analyses, results, and conclusions.

3 Comparative analysis of public engagement methods and approaches

3.1 Overview of sources used

As already mentioned, for the elaboration of the present deliverable, an accurate analysis of the methodologies and approaches presented in different sources as already indicated in the previous chapter has been carried out. This allowed the identification of eleven methods particularly suitable to be applied in participatory water / NBS governance in island settings. These methods span the spectrum of public participation defined by IAP2⁸, starting from informing and moving to consulting, involving, collaborating and, finally, empowering stakeholders.

Also, the publications and project outputs produced by ALDA constitute a complementary and equally important body of evidence for this chapter. However, they differ in nature and purpose from methodological handbooks or typological frameworks such as those produced by Involve or the OECD.

ALDA sources are predominantly:

- practice-based and project-oriented,
- grounded in real-world applications at the local and regional level,
- focused on democratic innovation, capacity-building, and institutional learning,
- often embedded within specific policy, territorial, or thematic contexts.

As such, ALDA publications do not typically present engagement methods as standardised, step-by-step models. Instead, they document how participatory and deliberative approaches are adapted, combined, and implemented in concrete governance settings, highlighting enabling conditions, institutional arrangements, and lessons-learnt from practice.

In light of these differences, sources are used in this chapter according to a clear and transparent division of roles. Most of the sources that will be later detailed in the next chapter are used as primary analytical references to define each engagement methodology; clarify its objectives, scope, and level of participation; and describe typical implementation phases, tools, and expected outcomes. ALDA sources are used, instead, as practice-oriented and contextual references to illustrate how the same methodologies are operationalised in local and regional governance contexts; highlight capacity-building dimensions, institutional constraints, and enabling factors; and provide examples of democratic innovation, stakeholder empowerment, and long-term engagement processes.

3.2 Overview of methods and approaches identified

The following table lists the eleven participatory methodologies and approaches that have been identified as particularly interesting to be applied in the GENESIS pilot's sites. The

⁸ IAP2 n.d. Op. cit.

table is intended as a summary and overview of the descriptions that are provided below in Chapter 3 for comparison and quick reference purposes. It is worth specifying that the identified methods differ in complexity and structure, ranging from those consisting of a single activity over a limited timeframe, such as Focus Groups and World Café, to methods composed of multiple activities that require a longer time span and therefore represent a process rather than a single action. This is the case of Living Labs and Community Visioning methods.

Table 1. Comparative summary table of participatory methods suitable for NBS and water governance contexts.

Method	Level of Participation (IAP2)	Purpose / Typical Use	Strengths	Limitations
Citizen Assembly	Collaborate / Empower	Representative deliberation on policy or strategy.	Builds legitimacy; deep dialogue; produces structured recommendations.	Time- and resource-intensive; requires strong institutional commitment.
Citizen Forum	Involve / Collaborate (occasionally Empower)	Structured public dialogue to discuss policy themes and formulate shared recommendations.	Flexible and adaptable; strengthens dialogue between citizens and institutions; can generate policy-oriented outputs.	Impact depends on institutional follow-up; may attract mainly already engaged citizens; non-binding outcomes.
Citizen Jury	Collaborate	Informed small-group deliberation on technical issues.	Encourages understanding of complexity; focused and structured; manageable size; evidence-based discussion.	Limited representativeness; advisory role; requires expert input and facilitation.
Community Visioning	Involve	Collective development of shared goals.	Creates unity and local ownership.	Limited technical depth.
Consensus Conference	Collaborate	Dialogue between citizens and experts.	Bridges science and society.	Demanding preparation; requires skilled facilitation and expert availability; time-intensive.

Deliberative Workshop	Involve	Structured discussion for mutual learning.	Flexible, inclusive, easy to replicate. It can improve relationships between participants.	Limited policy influence if isolated. Possible unclear conclusions.
Focus Group	Consult	Targeted qualitative exploration.	High level of participant interaction due to the small size of the group; in-depth qualitative insights; useful for specific stakeholder groups.	Limited representativeness, advisory only; limited policy influence; heavily dependent on a skilled facilitator.
Living Lab	Collaborate / Empower	Real-world co-creation and experimentation.	High innovation potential; iterative learning; integrates users and institutions; practical outcomes.	Coordination-intensive; may require technical capacity, sustained funding and institutional commitment.
Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches	Inform / Involve (occasionally Collaborate)	Awareness-raising and community engagement through artistic, cultural and experiential activities linked to sustainability themes.	Highly accessible and inclusive; effective for youth and broad audiences; strengthens emotional engagement; suitable for small communities.	Requires facilitation; limited deliberative depth; outcomes often symbolic unless linked to policy processes; impact may be short-term.
Stakeholder Panel	Consult / Collaborate	Regular dialogue platform bringing together organised stakeholders and institutions.	Sustained participation; enhances coordination; builds trust; supports ongoing governance.	May privilege organised actors; risk of power imbalance and fatigue.

World Café	Consult / Involve	Structured small-group dialogue around guiding questions to generate shared insights through an informal, rotating dialogue.	Inclusive; dynamic; encourages broad participation, exchange, creativity and networking.	Limited depth; outputs may be general unless consolidated carefully; requires skilled facilitation; difficult to record and report.
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The first column of the table reports the name of the different methodologies, while the second column, “level of participation (IAP2)” categorises the methodologies based on the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) Spectrum, previously presented. The assignment of the different levels of participation has been carried out by analysing the descriptions of the different methodologies and matching them with the definitions of the level of participation provided by IAP2.

The third column of the table presents the typical use or purpose of the methodology, while the following two columns detail the main strengths and the limitations of the methodology.

In the following paragraphs, the eleven methods and related features will be detailed. It is relevant to highlight that the level of analytical detail across the engagement methods presented in this chapter reflects their own nature and features and maturity of available methodological sources. In particular, while some methods - such as Citizen Assemblies, Citizen Juries, and World Café - are documented as standalone methodologies and related sources provide detailed procedural models, clearly defined phases, and extensive evidence of application across policy domains, other methods - including Focus Groups, Deliberative Workshops, and visual or experimental formats (categorised in this deliverable under Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches) - are more frequently documented as embedded components of broader participatory or governance processes. Practice-oriented sources such as those produced by ALDA tend to integrate these methods flexibly within local democratic innovation, capacity-building, or project-based contexts, rather than presenting them as fully standardised models. As a result, the chapter combines detailed methodological descriptions where canonical guidance exists with more interpretative and practice-informed explanations where methods are applied in a contextual and adaptive manner.

Below, the eleven selected methods are presented following this structure:

- Method overview and rationale
- Conditions for implementation
- Process and development phases
- Tools and supporting instruments
- Expected outcomes
- Practice-based insights from ALDA

In the following paragraphs, the different methodologies listed in the table above will be detailed in dedicated sheets by providing a method overview and rationale for each of them, the conditions for implementation, the methods’ process and development phases, tools and supporting instruments and expected outcomes. In addition, practice-based insights from ALDA’s experience in the use of the different methods will be presented. In order to elaborate the following sheets, different sources have been consulted spanning

from the Involve platform⁹, to publications of key institutions such as OECD¹⁰ and the Council of Europe¹¹, documents and deliverables produced in the frame of other European Projects such as REAL DEAL¹², AQUATIK-EU¹³, ClimART¹⁴, CLIMentines¹⁵, Decide¹⁶, GreenSAM¹⁷, UNaLab¹⁸..... Several academic and scientific papers have also been consulted (Chitakira 2023¹⁹; Walzer and Hamm 2010²⁰; Gustavsson et al. 2025²¹; Nielsen et al. 2006²²). In addition, dedicated platforms and websites have been consulted for instance the ENoLL website²³. Finally, as already mentioned, for each methodology described in this chapter, ALDA sources²⁴ are mobilised in a dedicated, concluding paragraph that situates the method

⁹ Involve n.d. Op. cit.

¹⁰ OECD 2020 Innovative Citizen Participation Op. Cit and OECD 2022 Building Trust to Reinforce Op. cit.

¹¹ [Council of Europe Civil Participation \(2019\). CODE OF GOOD PRACTICE FOR CIVIL PARTICIPATION IN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS - REVISED.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹² [REAL DEAL. \(n.d.\) CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT IN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY: Policy Recommendations from EU-wide citizens' forums. Horizon Project.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹³ [AQUATIK-EU \(2025\). Toolkit guide on water awareness sustainability education and valorization of water heritages. Deliverable 1.2 CERV Project.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹⁴ [CLIMART \(2023\). INTELLECTUAL OUTPUT 1 CLIMATE CHANGE LEARNING MATERIAL AND GUIDE MANUAL FOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS. Erasmus+ Project](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2025).

¹⁵ [CLIMentines \(2025\). The Climentines Youth Worker's Guide to Climate Action. Erasmus+ Project.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹⁶ [Decide \(2022\) DEmocratic Compact: Improving Democracy in Europe. Europe for Citizens Project.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹⁷ [GreenSam Green Silver Age Mobility, Concept paper: Citizen Forum, Interreg Baltic Sea Region](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹⁸ [Dubovik, M., et al \(2024\). Nature-Based Solutions Implementation Handbook: A Summary for Practitioners. Horizon Europe project UNaLab.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

¹⁹ Chitakira, M. (2024). *Chapter 35: Community visioning in Handbook of Social Impact Assessment and Management. 547-561.* Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781802208870.00046>

²⁰ Walzer N. & Hamm G. (2010). *Community visioning programs: processes and outcomes.* 41:2, 152-155. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15575331003610005>

²¹ [Gustavsson, M., Solnør, S. and Rønningen, K. \(eds.\) 2025. Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies: How methods and methodologies contribute to equitable coastal transition through empowerment and inclusivity. Deliverable 5.2, Horizon Europe project EmpowerUs.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

²² [Nielsen A. P. et al. \(2026\). Consensus Conference Manual, LEI, The Hague.](#) Accessed: 25 February 2026).

²³ [European Network of Living Labs \(EnoLL\) \(n.d.\) Homepage.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

²⁴ [ALDA \(2024\). ALDA TOWARDS 2030. Localising the SDGs: Good practices from Europe and the Neighbourhood areas.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

[ALDA 2024. A WEALTH OF EXPERTISE. Toolkit for Local Authorities to successfully engage citizens.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

[ALDA \(2015\). Supporting European ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026). (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

[ALDA \(2023\). Toolkit for Local Authorities – How to engage citizens at the local level.](#) (Accessed: 25

GENESIS - D2.2 Guidelines for public engagement and dialogue within applied experiences and governance practices, without redefining or altering the methodological core derived from the primary analytical references.

February 2026).
[LADDER \(2016\). BRINGING GLOBAL ISSUES AT THE LOCAL LEVEL RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS THROUGH GRASS-ROOTS LEVEL INITIATIVES.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

3.2.1 Citizen Assembly

Citizen Assembly

Method overview and rationale

Citizen Assemblies are structured deliberative processes in which a group of citizens, selected to reflect the demographic composition of a given population, examine a defined policy issue over an extended period and formulate collective recommendations. According to OECD, citizen assemblies are a form of deliberative mini-public that combines representative selection, structured learning, facilitated deliberation, and formal outputs. Assemblies are typically larger and longer than citizen juries. They may involve 50-150 participants and extend over multiple sessions. Participants receive balanced briefing materials, hear from experts and stakeholders, deliberate in small groups and plenary sessions, and produce recommendations intended to inform public decision-making. Involvement describes citizen assemblies as processes that enable informed public judgment on complex issues by providing participants with time, evidence, and structured facilitation. The Council of Europe situates such mechanisms within higher levels of participation, where structured dialogue and partnership enhance democratic legitimacy. Citizen Assemblies are topic-neutral but are commonly used for issues characterised by complexity, long-term implications, and competing values. Their relevance to environmental governance or water management, therefore, depends on the issue under examination.

Conditions for implementation

Effective citizen assemblies require robust organisational design. First, participant selection must be based on stratified random sampling to ensure demographic representativeness across criteria such as age, gender, geography, and socio-economic background. Second, the mandate and influence of the assembly must be clearly defined. Participants must understand the scope of their role and how their recommendations will be considered by public authorities. Third, balanced and accessible information must be provided. Assemblies typically include expert presentations, written briefing materials, and opportunities for participants to request additional evidence. Fourth, professional facilitation is essential. Moderators guide small-group discussions, ensure equitable participation, and manage disagreement constructively. Fifth, transparency and communication mechanisms must be established. Public reporting, livestreaming where appropriate, and formal response commitments strengthen legitimacy and trust.

Process and development phases

Citizen assemblies generally follow a structured multi-phase process. A design and preparation phase including the definition of the policy question, establishment of governance and advisory structures, recruitment of participants through stratified selection, and preparation of balanced briefing materials. A consequent learning phase during which expert makes presentations and stakeholders provide input, integrated with question-and-answer sessions, and the distribution of supporting documentation. A third deliberation phase consisting in facilitated small-group discussions, exploration of options, trade-offs, and values, and a plenary synthesis session. A fourth recommendation phase of drafting of recommendations, review and amendment, and formal approval by participants. The final phase is the publication and institutional response with the public release of recommendations and the formal response from authorities. OECD highlights that effective assemblies allocate sufficient time for learning and deliberation, distinguishing them from shorter consultative formats.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications emphasise representative participation, structured deliberation, and linkage of citizen input to institutional processes as core principles of participatory governance. While not always labelled explicitly as “Citizen Assemblies,” similar large-scale deliberative formats are used to foster inclusive dialogue and structured recommendation processes. ALDA practice underscores the importance of institutional commitment to respond formally to citizen recommendations in order to sustain trust and engagement.

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational instruments include:

- Stratified random selection tools
- Briefing documents prepared in accessible language
- Expert hearings
- Facilitated small-group discussions
- Digital platforms for documentation and transparency
- Structured reporting templates for recommendations

In environmental contexts, evidence may include ecological data, scenario modelling, cost-benefit assessments, and monitoring indicators.

Expected outcomes

Citizen assemblies produce structured and collective recommendations grounded in informed deliberation.

Tangible outputs include:

- Written recommendations
- Prioritised options
- Conditional policy proposals

OECD notes that assemblies can enhance policy legitimacy and public trust when authorities demonstrate responsiveness and transparency in addressing outcomes.

The deliberative nature of assemblies also contributes to relational outcomes such as increased civic knowledge, mutual understanding, and strengthened democratic culture.

3.2.2 Citizen Forum

Citizen Forum

Method overview and rationale

The Citizen Forum is a participation tool that represents a structured dialogue-based methodology that facilitates active dialogue among citizens, politicians, professional urban/rural planners, NGOs and other decision makers. From a methodological perspective, the Citizen Forum works as a hybrid deliberative format that combines different elements of participatory workshops, co-creation sessions, and stakeholder dialogue into a single, thematic “working group”, where participants debate and reflect in-depth on specific issues or topics. The rationale of the tool is to strengthen development planning processes by promoting bottom-up participation while simultaneously ensuring institutional involvement. On one hand, the methodology allows citizens to directly express needs, expectations, and feedback related to planning and policy processes; on the other hand, it actively involves policymakers and politicians in participatory planning. This structure contributes to improving the quality of dialogue between citizens and the public sector, which is essential for the legitimacy of decision-making processes. This dimension of dialogue is particularly effective in the context of planning green solutions, including Nature-Based Solutions. By facilitating the active and inclusive participation of diverse stakeholder groups, the Citizen Forum supports the co-creation of solutions that can better suit citizens’ and stakeholders’ needs and facilitate a stronger long-term acceptance of the proposed interventions within the community.

Conditions for implementation

A Citizen Forum is suitable for bigger audiences, generally ranging from approximately 30 to 100 participants, depending on participation techniques, concerns, format and availability. This makes it quite effective for community-wide discussions in pilot territories where green infrastructure is planned. It is also relevant to note that the methodology is multi-stakeholder at its core; it is advisable to identify and involve a broad range of actors, including citizens, policymakers, planners, NGOs, experts, and institutional representatives. A Citizen Forum usually lasts for a full day, and participants can expect to be highly involved. Preparation time is considerable and can take around three months, depending on different factors such as stakeholder recruitment, selection of participatory techniques, preparation of materials, and logistics. In alignment with other participatory methodologies, the success of the citizen forums strongly relies on early engagement and effective stakeholder mapping and communication. The organisation of a Citizen Forum requires facilitators - possibly with experience in conflict management, dedicated venues, and strong organisational coordination. From a process perspective, Citizen Forums can be used across all stages of a participatory cycle: planning and development, implementation or evaluation.

Process and development phases

Citizen Forums generally follow a structured, yet flexible process aimed at connecting public dialogue with institutional action. A first design phase includes the definition of the thematic focus, the clarification of objectives, the identification of organising partners (local authorities and civil society), and the confirmation of the level of institutional commitment to follow-up. A second mobilisation phase involves stakeholder mapping, public communication and participant recruitment. Forums may combine open participation with targeted outreach to ensure inclusiveness, particularly of youth, civil society actors and underrepresented groups. The third phase consists of information and facilitated dialogue. Introductory inputs frame the topic, followed by moderated discussions organised in plenary or small groups. Exchanges focus on identifying priorities, challenges and potential actions, often structured around guiding questions. A fourth consolidation phase translates discussions into structured outputs such as recommendations, joint statements or priority lists. Draft results may be collectively reviewed to strengthen ownership. The final phase concerns public communication and institutional response, including the dissemination of results and formal feedback from authorities on how the forum's conclusions will inform policies or future initiatives. Transparent follow-up is highlighted as essential to maintain trust and avoid participation fatigue.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA's experience in citizen participation shows that engagement methods are most effective when adapted to the specific territorial and institutional context, rather than implemented as isolated, one-off activities. ALDA's work and experience highlight the need for

Tools and supporting instruments

The Citizen Forum does not rely on a single facilitation tool but rather works as an umbrella format that integrates multiple participatory and deliberative tools within a structured thematic event.

These tools can include:

- Participatory Workshop
- World Café
- Fishbowl Debate
- Hands-on Planning

This structure allows organisers to adapt the forum design to the specific thematic focus and stakeholder composition. Other supporting instruments can include interviews, workshops, presentations, and facilitated discussion sessions, all of which contribute to structured knowledge exchange and co-creation processes. As already mentioned, Citizen Forums are typically organised as full-day events. What is relevant to note is that the analysis phase afterwards is an essential methodological tool, as it transforms qualitative dialogue into actionable insights for planning and governance

Expected outcomes

The Citizen Forum is expected to generate dialogue and cooperation at the local level, as it creates a structured space for interaction among citizens, policymakers, experts, and other stakeholders.

long-term engagement, stakeholder ownership, and the use of flexible participatory formats tailored to local needs. Accordingly, Citizen Forums are effective when contextualised in recurring dialogue spaces and integrated into broader engagement strategies that support inclusivity, trust-building, and ongoing interaction with stakeholders.

3.2.3 Citizen Jury

Citizen Jury

Method overview and rationale

Citizen Juries are structured deliberative processes in which a small group of citizens examines a specific issue, hears from expert witnesses, deliberates collectively, and produces recommendations. According to Involve, a citizen jury typically consists of 12–24 participants selected to reflect a cross-section of the community, who meet over several days to consider evidence and deliberate before reaching conclusions. The method is designed to simulate a jury model: participants are presented with balanced information, question experts directly, and deliberate independently before formulating recommendations. OECD identifies citizen juries as deliberative mini-publics that strengthen democratic legitimacy by enabling informed citizen engagement beyond traditional consultation. Citizen Juries differ from focus groups in that they are designed to produce structured outputs, and from consensus conferences in that they are often shorter in duration and more focused on producing recommendations rather than a broad consensus statement. In environmental and water governance contexts, citizen juries are particularly relevant when decisions involve trade-offs, contested priorities, or alternative policy options requiring structured public reasoning.

Conditions for implementation

Effective citizen juries require specific design elements. First, participant selection must ensure representativeness. Involve emphasises the importance of stratified recruitment to reflect demographic diversity and avoid over-representation of organised interests. Second, balanced and accessible information must be provided. Jurors receive briefing materials and hear from expert witnesses representing different perspectives. OECD underlines that deliberative processes require sufficient time and information to enable informed judgment. Third, independent and skilled facilitation is essential. Moderators guide discussion, ensure equal participation, manage disagreement constructively, and maintain focus on the defined question. Fourth, clarity regarding the mandate and influence of the jury is necessary. Participants must understand whether their recommendations are advisory, consultative, or linked to formal decision-making processes. Fifth, a clear response mechanism must be established. Authorities commissioning the jury should commit to responding publicly to its recommendations.

Process and development phases

Citizen Juries generally follow a structured sequence. A first preparation phase comprising the definition of the policy question, the establishment of an organising team, the recruitment of jurors,

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools commonly used include:

- Briefing documents prepared in accessible language
- Structured expert hearings

the identification of expert witnesses and the preparation of balanced briefing materials. A second phase of information and hearing during which the experts present evidence, the jurors question the witnesses, and clarifications and counter-arguments are discussed. The third phase is the deliberation one: the jurors deliberate in closed sessions, the facilitators support structured reflection, and options, trade-offs, and priorities are examined. There is then a recommendation phase when the jury drafts and agrees upon recommendations and the outputs are documented in written form. During the final phase of public presentation and response, the recommendations are publicly presented, and the commissioning authorities provide a response. In NbS and water governance contexts, juries may examine alternative site options, prioritisation of ecosystem services, allocation of resources, or evaluation of proposed interventions.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications emphasise structured citizen deliberation as a tool for strengthening democratic engagement and linking citizen input to policy processes. Although not always labelled explicitly as “Citizen Juries,” similar formats combining expert hearings, facilitated discussion, and documented outputs are used in participatory governance initiatives. ALDA experience highlights the importance of transparency in recruitment, clarity about decision-making influence, and visible institutional response to recommendations.

- Facilitated deliberation sessions
- Decision-support tools such as option comparison matrices
- Formal reporting templates to document recommendations

Where environmental issues are concerned, ecological data summaries, risk assessments, or scenario projections may support informed discussion.

Expected outcomes

Citizen Juries produce tangible and structured outputs.

The primary output is a set of written recommendations reflecting the considered judgment of the jurors. These may include prioritised options, conditional support for proposals, or identification of safeguards. OECD notes that deliberative mini-publics can improve policy quality and public trust when participants are provided with balanced information and when institutions respond transparently to outcomes. In environmental governance contexts, citizen juries can enhance the legitimacy of decisions involving ecological trade-offs by demonstrating that informed citizens have examined the evidence and articulated reasoned conclusions.

3.2.4 Community Visioning

Community Visioning

Method overview and rationale

Community Visioning is a structured participatory planning process through which community members collectively articulate a shared long-term future for their territory and define the priorities needed to achieve it. It involves broad-based community input, reflection on existing conditions, and the formulation of a clear and aspirational but actionable future direction. According to Walzer and Hamm, community visioning initiatives typically combine analysis of past and current trends, exploration of alternative futures, development of measurable goals, and identification of timelines and responsibilities. Chitakira further emphasises that visioning is not merely symbolic; it is intended to guide long-term development pathways and align community aspirations with planning and investment processes. In environmental and Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) contexts, visioning is particularly relevant where long-term ecological, social, and economic objectives must be balanced. The IUCN Global Standard for NBS stresses the importance of inclusive, participatory governance and alignment with long-term sustainability objectives. Community Visioning contributes to this by enabling stakeholders to define shared objectives for territorial resilience, ecosystem restoration, and sustainable resource management. Similarly, the UNaLab Implementation Handbook highlights the need for early stakeholder engagement and co-definition of objectives in NBS planning processes.

Conditions for implementation

First, inclusive participation is essential. Both Walzer and Hamm and Chitakira stress that successful visioning initiatives involve a broad cross-section of the community, ensuring that different social groups, interests, and perspectives are represented. Second, facilitation must be structured and neutral. Chitakira notes that facilitators play a critical role in guiding discussions, managing power dynamics, and ensuring that dominant voices do not overshadow others. Transparent communication about objectives and expected outcomes is necessary to avoid confusion between vision statements, goals, and implementation measures. Third, integration with formal planning processes increases effectiveness. Walzer and Hamm underline that visioning initiatives are more likely to succeed when linked to concrete strategies, monitoring mechanisms, and follow-up actions. In NBS implementation contexts, this aligns with guidance provided in the Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies, which highlights the importance of embedding participatory processes within governance structures and ensuring institutional commitment.

Process and development phases

While formats vary, the literature identifies common phases in community visioning processes. Chitakira describes a phased

Tools and supporting instruments

Community Visioning is typically operationalised through:

- Multi-stakeholder workshops and public meetings

approach including, first, the identification of current concerns and the definition of the timeframe for the vision; second, a collective analysis of community assets, challenges, and opportunities; third, the formulation of a shared vision through group discussions and visual or narrative articulation; and fourth, the consolidation and validation of the vision through collective review. Walzer and Hamm similarly describe processes that combine trend analysis, goal-setting, strategy development, and identification of measurable milestones, followed by mechanisms for tracking progress. In NBS co-production processes, Nature4Cities project highlights the importance of iterative engagement and collaborative framing of objectives, ensuring that community visions inform design and implementation choices.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA's participatory planning initiatives emphasise that visioning processes are most effective when formally anchored within local or regional strategies and followed by clear implementation pathways. ALDA publications underline the importance of:

- Translating vision statements into operational plans
- Ensuring political endorsement and administrative follow-up
- Maintaining stakeholder engagement beyond the initial visioning phase

This practice-based perspective reinforces the academic finding that visioning should not remain aspirational but should guide concrete governance action.

- Facilitated small-group discussions to enable inclusive participation
- Visualisation tools and mapping exercises to articulate spatial priorities and future scenarios
- Co-production workshops, as recommended in NBS implementation guidance

The selection of tools should consider local context, literacy levels, and available institutional capacity.

Expected outcomes

Community Visioning produces both strategic and relational outcomes. On a strategic level, it results in a collectively endorsed long-term vision, often articulated in written form and accompanied by goals or priority areas. Such outputs can inform territorial planning, conservation strategies, or NBS investment priorities. On a relational level, visioning strengthens communication, trust, and shared ownership among participants. Walzer and Hamm report that participants frequently value improvements in collaboration and leadership development as important outcomes of visioning processes. In environmental governance contexts, aligning local aspirations with sustainability objectives contributes to long-term stewardship and resilience, consistent with the participatory governance principles of the IUCN Global Standard for NBS.

3.2.5 Consensus Conference

Consensus Conference

Method overview and rationale

Consensus Conferences are structured deliberative processes in which a panel of lay citizens examines a specific policy or technological issue, questions experts in public hearings, deliberates collectively, and produces a written statement summarising its conclusions. According to the Consensus Conference Manual, the method is designed to enable non-expert citizens to engage with complex issues through a staged process that combines information, questioning, and deliberation. The Manual describes the core objective as facilitating informed public judgment by allowing citizens to scrutinise expert knowledge and articulate collective conclusions in their own words. The CLIMentines Guide presents consensus conferences as participatory mechanisms aimed at enhancing democratic legitimacy by creating structured dialogue between citizens and experts in a transparent format. Unlike stakeholder panels, which involve organised interests, consensus conferences typically rely on a citizen panel selected to reflect diversity within the community and to operate independently from institutional or sectoral positions.

Conditions for implementation

Effective implementation requires specific organisational conditions. First, an independent organising body or steering committee is established. According to the Manual, this body oversees topic definition, expert selection, logistics, and procedural integrity. Second, citizen panel selection must ensure diversity and independence. The Manual emphasises transparent recruitment procedures and avoidance of conflicts of interest. Third, balanced expert input is essential. Experts representing different perspectives are invited to provide written materials and participate in public hearings. The CLIMentines Guide stresses the importance of ensuring that information is accessible and comprehensible to non-specialists. Fourth, facilitation must be neutral and structured. Moderators guide both the public hearing and the private deliberation phases to ensure equal participation and clarity of discussion. Finally, institutional clarity is required. The commissioning authority should define how the final statement will be received, disseminated, and responded to.

Process and development phases

Both the Consensus Conference Manual and the CLIMentines Guide outline a staged process composed of distinct phases. First, a preparation phase for the definition of the topic and scope, the establishment of an organising structure, the recruitment of a citizen panel, the selection of experts, and the distribution of preparatory materials. Second, a public hearing phase when the experts present evidence in open sessions, the citizen panel members question experts directly, and clarifications and counter-arguments are allowed. The third is the deliberation phase, when citizens deliberate in closed sessions without the experts' presence, the facilitators support structured discussion, and the panel drafts a written statement. In the final phase of finalisation and publication, the panel agrees on a final document, the statement is presented publicly, and the authorities are expected to respond. The Manual emphasises the importance of separating expert input from citizen deliberation to preserve the autonomy of the panel's conclusions.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

A review of ALDA publications indicates that while structured citizen–expert dialogues are frequently implemented, explicit reference to “Consensus Conferences” as a named methodology is limited. Where similar formats are applied, emphasis is placed on transparent facilitation, structured debate, and formal integration of outputs into policy processes, consistent with the procedural logic described in the Manual and the CLIMentines Guide.

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational instruments include:

- Written briefing materials prepared in accessible language
- Structured public hearings
- Moderated small-group or plenary deliberation sessions
- Drafting sessions supported by facilitators
- Formal publication of the consensus statement

The CLIMentines Guide also highlights transparency tools such as public dissemination events and accessible reporting formats to ensure broader visibility of outcomes.

Expected outcomes

The primary output is a written consensus statement drafted and approved by the citizen panel. This document typically summarises key findings, areas of agreement, and recommendations. The Manual identifies additional outcomes, including:

- Increased public understanding of the issue
- Structured interaction between citizens and experts
- Enhanced transparency of technical debates

The CLIMentines Guide emphasises that the public presentation of conclusions strengthens the visibility and accountability of participatory processes. OECD recognises deliberative processes involving informed citizens as mechanisms capable of improving policy legitimacy when institutions formally engage with the outcomes.

3.2.6 Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches

Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches

Method overview and rationale

Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches refer to structured engagement processes that use artistic expression, cultural production, and creative co-creation as tools to stimulate active citizen involvement in governance issues. Rather than relying exclusively on formal deliberation, these approaches mobilise theatre, visual arts, storytelling, mapping, exhibitions, and community-based cultural practices to enable participants to express experiences, values, and visions related to shared challenges. The AQUATIK-EU Toolkit on water awareness describes participatory mental mapping, value timelines, and community-based heritage activities as tools that allow citizens to actively represent and interpret their relationship with water, producing visual and narrative outputs that can inform dialogue and planning. Similarly, the ClimART methodological manuals outline art-based learning methodologies in which participants become co-creators of performances, installations, or visual outputs addressing climate change, moving beyond passive awareness-raising toward active civic expression. In participatory governance contexts, such approaches create spaces where experiential knowledge, cultural identity, and environmental values can be articulated collectively, supporting more inclusive and context-sensitive decision-making processes.

Conditions for implementation

Effective creative and cultural participatory processes require specific enabling conditions. First, there must be a clearly defined thematic focus linked to a governance challenge, such as water stewardship, environmental sustainability, or climate resilience. Second, facilitators with both participatory and creative competencies are necessary. ClimART emphasises the importance of trained facilitators capable of guiding artistic processes while maintaining thematic coherence and inclusive participation. Third, safe and inclusive spaces must be created to allow participants to express personal perspectives and experiences without fear of judgment. Fourth, institutional linkage mechanisms should be foreseen. Outputs such as exhibitions, performances, or visual artefacts should be connected to public events, policy dialogues, or planning discussions to ensure that creative expression informs governance processes.

Process and development phases

While formats vary, creative participatory approaches typically follow a staged process. Initially, there is a framing and thematic introduction during which participants are introduced to the topic (e.g., water sustainability, climate

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools documented in the sources include:

- Participatory mental mapping exercises
- Value timeline construction workshops
- Art-based learning workshops and performance labs

impacts) through interactive discussion or stimulus materials. Afterwards, there is an exploration and creative production phase when participants engage in structured creative activities such as the mental mapping of water-related experiences, the development of value timelines, the collective script writing or theatrical creation, the visual storytelling or artistic installations. A phase of collective reflection and dialogue follows when creative outputs are presented and discussed within the group. Facilitators guide reflection on emerging themes, shared concerns, and potential solutions. The final phase is a public presentation or integration into governance processes. Outputs may be exhibited, performed, or presented to wider audiences, including policymakers or local authorities. This phase transforms creative production into civic contribution. In the AQUATIK-EU context, participatory mental maps and value timelines are intended to support multi-stakeholder dialogue around water heritage and sustainability.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications document the use of cultural events, participatory campaigns, and community-based activities to mobilise citizens around sustainability and governance themes. In several initiatives linked to the SDGs and environmental awareness, cultural and public engagement activities have been used to stimulate dialogue and broaden participation. These experiences underline the importance of connecting creative outputs to structured follow-up processes to ensure that artistic engagement contributes to governance outcomes rather than remaining symbolic.

- Methodological guidelines for activating community engagement through artistic production
- Public exhibitions or performances as dissemination and dialogue platforms. These tools generate tangible artefacts (maps, scripts, performances, visual materials) that can be documented and integrated into planning or awareness strategies.

Expected outcomes

Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches produce both expressive and governance-relevant outputs.

Tangible outcomes include:

- Visual representations of community relationships with water or the environment
- Co-created performances addressing environmental themes
- Documented narratives and mapped knowledge
- Exhibitions or public events presenting community perspectives

Process outcomes include:

- Increased environmental awareness
- Strengthened sense of ownership and identity
- Enhanced dialogue between citizens and institutions

The AQUATIK-EU toolkit explicitly positions creative exercises as tools to connect heritage, sustainability, and community engagement in water-related contexts. ClimART materials emphasise that art-based methodologies move participants from awareness to active engagement, fostering empowerment and collective reflection.

3.2.7 Deliberative Workshop

Deliberative Workshop

Method overview and rationale

Deliberative Workshops are structured participatory formats designed to enable participants to engage collectively with a defined issue through informed discussion, reflection, and exchange of arguments. According to Involve, deliberative approaches differ from general consultation formats because they provide participants with time, information, and facilitation necessary to consider evidence, weigh trade-offs, and explore different viewpoints before forming conclusions. Unlike focus groups, which primarily explore perceptions, deliberative workshops aim to support reasoned discussion and, where appropriate, the development of shared positions or structured outputs. OECD recognises deliberative processes as mechanisms that strengthen policy legitimacy by enabling informed citizen engagement beyond simple opinion collection. In participatory governance frameworks, deliberative workshops correspond to dialogic and partnership-oriented engagement levels, where participants are invited to reflect critically and collectively rather than merely provide feedback. In the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and water governance, deliberative workshops are relevant where ecological, social, and economic considerations must be discussed together and where participants need structured opportunities to examine trade-offs, priorities, and implementation pathways.

Conditions for implementation

Effective deliberative workshops require careful preparation and facilitation. First, participants must receive balanced and accessible information in advance or during the session. Deliberation presupposes informed discussion; therefore, briefing materials, presentations, or expert inputs must be structured and comprehensible. Second, the scope and objectives of the workshop must be clearly defined. Participants should understand whether the goal is to generate recommendations, refine proposals, prioritise options, or explore scenarios. Third, facilitation must be neutral and structured. Moderators should encourage equal participation, manage disagreement constructively, and ensure discussions remain focused on the defined topic. Fourth, group composition should reflect relevant stakeholder diversity. Depending on objectives, workshops may include citizens, experts, public officials, or mixed groups. Fifth, documentation and follow-up mechanisms must be established. Clear recording of conclusions, dissenting views, and agreed priorities is essential to ensure transparency and institutional uptake.

Process and development phases

Deliberative Workshops typically follow a structured sequence: a first preparatory phase for the definition of objectives and

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools commonly used in deliberative workshops include:

expected outputs, the identification and recruitment of participants, the preparation of balanced briefing materials, and the design of an agenda and a facilitation plan. Secondly, there is an information phase for the presentation of relevant evidence or project proposals and clarification questions from participants. Thirdly, in a small-group deliberation phase, the participants discuss defined questions in moderated groups; trade-offs, risks, and alternatives are explored; points of convergence and divergence are identified. The plenary synthesis phase follows, when the groups report back, collective discussion consolidates key findings, and - where appropriate - prioritisation or structured recommendations are developed. Finally, there is a phase of documentation and feedback, when the outcomes are summarised in a written report and the participants are informed of how outputs will be used. In NBS and water governance contexts, such workshops may address site selection criteria, ecosystem service priorities, funding allocation options, or monitoring indicators.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications emphasise structured participatory workshops as tools for strengthening democratic dialogue and collective decision-making. Such workshops often combine information-sharing sessions with moderated group discussion, ensuring that citizen contributions are informed and systematically documented. ALDA experience underlines the importance of clearly communicating the influence of workshop outcomes on policy processes in order to maintain trust and avoid consultation fatigue.

- Briefing documents and evidence summaries
- Structured discussion guides
- Scenario comparison matrices
- Prioritisation tools (e.g., ranking exercises)
- Visual aids such as maps or project diagrams
- Synthesis templates for reporting

In environmental contexts, ecological data summaries, ecosystem service assessments, or impact projections may support informed deliberation.

Expected outcomes

Deliberative Workshops produce structured outputs that reflect informed discussion rather than spontaneous opinion. Tangible outputs may include:

- Prioritised options
- Refined project proposals
- Structured recommendations
- Identification of acceptable trade-offs

OECD highlights that deliberative processes can improve policy quality when participants are given time and information to reflect before forming conclusions. In environmental governance contexts, deliberative workshops support alignment between technical feasibility and social acceptability by enabling participants to examine evidence collectively.

3.2.8 Focus Group

Focus Group

Method overview and rationale

Focus Groups are structured small-group discussions designed to explore participants' perceptions, experiences, attitudes, and reactions to a specific issue. According to Involve, focus groups are typically composed of 6–12 participants and are facilitated to encourage open discussion around defined questions or themes. The method is particularly useful for gaining qualitative insights into how different groups understand a topic, identify concerns, or prioritise issues. Unlike deliberative mini-publics, focus groups do not aim to produce collective recommendations or consensus statements. Instead, they are designed to generate in-depth understanding of stakeholder perspectives, identify areas of agreement or disagreement, and uncover contextual factors that may influence policy acceptance. In governance contexts, focus groups are commonly used during early planning phases to inform policy design, test proposals, or refine communication strategies. The Council of Europe's Code of Good Practice situates such methods within consultation and dialogue processes, where authorities seek structured input from affected groups. In the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and water governance, focus groups are relevant for understanding community perceptions of environmental risks, local knowledge of ecosystems, concerns about infrastructure interventions, and expectations regarding benefits and trade-offs.

Conditions for implementation

Effective focus groups require careful preparation and facilitation. First, participant selection must be purposive and transparent. Groups should be composed according to relevant criteria such as stakeholder category, demographic characteristics, or territorial representation, depending on the objective of the discussion. In some cases, separate focus groups may be organised for different categories to ensure open discussion. Second, discussion objectives and guiding questions must be clearly defined. Focus Groups are most effective when structured around specific themes rather than general conversation. Third, facilitation must ensure balanced participation. A neutral moderator is responsible for encouraging quieter participants, managing dominant voices, and maintaining focus on the topic. Fourth, documentation procedures must be established. Notes, audio recordings (where consent is provided), and structured summaries are necessary to capture insights accurately. Finally, expectations must be managed. Participants should understand the purpose of the discussion and how their input will be used in subsequent stages.

Process and development phases

Focus Groups generally follow a structured but flexible process. First there is a preparation phase to define the objectives, identify and recruit the participants and develop a discussion guide. Secondly, a phase of introduction and framing for the explanation of purpose and confidentiality, and the presentation of the topic or stimulus materials. A facilitated discussion follows, comprising a guided exploration of key questions, encouraged interaction among participants, and clarification and probing by the moderator. The final phase of synthesis and closing consists of a summary of the main points, the opportunity for any final remarks and the clarification of the next steps. In NBS and water governance contexts, focus groups may be used at different stages, including problem definition, co-design refinement, or evaluation of pilot interventions.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications frequently refer to small-group consultations and thematic discussion groups as tools to gather community input and strengthen participatory governance. Such practices emphasise the importance of inclusive facilitation, clear communication of objectives, and structured reporting to ensure that discussions inform policy processes. ALDA experience suggests that focus groups are particularly useful in early stages of participatory processes to identify priorities and potential areas of conflict before moving toward more structured deliberative formats.

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools commonly used in focus groups include:

- Structured discussion guides
- Visual prompts, maps, or project designs to stimulate discussion
- Audio recording or detailed note-taking for accurate documentation
- Summary templates to synthesise key findings

Where environmental or infrastructure projects are discussed, visual materials such as site maps or conceptual drawings can support understanding and facilitate informed discussion.

Expected outcomes

Focus Groups primarily generate qualitative insights rather than formal decisions. Tangible outputs include:

- Thematic summaries of stakeholder perceptions
- Identification of concerns, expectations, and perceived risks
- Clarification of social acceptance factors

These insights can inform subsequent design adjustments, communication strategies, or policy refinements. While focus groups do not produce binding recommendations, they contribute to evidence-based decision-making by highlighting contextual realities and stakeholder diversity. In environmental governance, this type of qualitative input supports alignment between technical planning and community expectations, particularly in contexts where local knowledge and perception of environmental change are relevant.

3.2.9 Living Lab

Living Lab

Method overview and rationale

Living Labs are collaborative, real-life innovation environments where public authorities, citizens, researchers, and private actors co-design, test, and refine solutions in real-world conditions. According to the European Network of Living Labs, Living Labs operate as open innovation ecosystems integrating research and innovation processes within public–private–people partnerships. The approach is characterised by experimentation in real settings, iterative feedback loops, and continuous stakeholder engagement. In the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Living Labs are frequently presented as implementation and testing environments that support co-creation and adaptive learning. The IUCN Global Standard for NBS highlights adaptive management, stakeholder inclusion, and monitoring as core components of effective NBS governance. Living Labs operationalise these principles by enabling solutions to be designed, piloted, and evaluated collaboratively in situ. Unlike deliberative mini-publics, Living Labs are not primarily decision-making forums but structured innovation processes focused on experimentation, co-production, and learning.

Conditions for implementation

Effective Living Labs require several enabling conditions. First, multi-actor partnerships must be established. The approach depends on collaboration among public authorities, research institutions, civil society, and, where relevant, private sector actors. Second, a defined real-life testing environment must be identified. Living Labs operate within a specific territorial or thematic context where solutions can be implemented and observed under actual conditions. Third, governance and coordination mechanisms must be clear. Roles, responsibilities, decision-making procedures, and communication channels should be defined at the outset. Fourth, monitoring and evaluation frameworks must be integrated from the beginning. The IUCN Standard emphasises the importance of measurable indicators and adaptive management. Living Labs require structured data collection and iterative review mechanisms. Finally, long-term institutional support is necessary to sustain experimentation beyond short-term pilot phases.

Process and development phases

While formats vary, Living Labs typically follow iterative stages. The first one is the co-definition of challenges and objectives, when stakeholders collectively define the problem and agree on shared objectives. The second one is the co-design of solutions:

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational instruments within Living Labs include:

- Co-design workshops
- Pilot demonstration sites
- Environmental and social monitoring indicators

participants collaboratively develop prototypes, strategies, or pilot interventions. Thirdly, solutions are deployed in the designated territory or environment in an implementation and real-life testing phase. The fourth phase is of monitoring and evaluation, when performance is assessed using agreed indicators, including environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The final phase consists of reflection and adaptation: results are reviewed collectively, and solutions are refined or scaled accordingly. The Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies stresses the importance of inclusive participation and iterative learning throughout NBS co-creation processes.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications emphasise co-creation, territorial experimentation, and participatory governance as core elements of local democracy initiatives. While not always labelled explicitly as “Living Labs,” similar approaches are used to pilot local solutions, foster stakeholder collaboration, and translate participatory processes into concrete actions. ALDA experiences highlight the importance of maintaining stakeholder engagement throughout implementation phases and ensuring that pilot initiatives are embedded in local governance frameworks.

- Participatory evaluation sessions
- Digital platforms for knowledge sharing and documentation

In NBS contexts, monitoring frameworks may include biodiversity indicators, ecosystem service assessments, and social acceptance measures.

Expected outcomes

Living Labs generate both tangible and process-oriented outcomes. Tangible outputs include:

- Tested and refined prototypes or NBS interventions
- Monitoring data and performance evidence
- Documented lessons-learnt

Process outcomes include:

- Strengthened stakeholder collaboration
- Increased local ownership of implemented solutions
- Enhanced institutional capacity for adaptive governance

The UNaLab guidance underlines that real-life testing environments support scaling and replication of successful NBS interventions.

3.2.10 Stakeholder Panel

Stakeholder Panel

Method overview and rationale

Stakeholder Panels are structured engagement mechanisms that bring together representatives of relevant stakeholder groups to provide ongoing input, advice, and feedback on a policy, programme, or project. According to Involve, stakeholder panels are typically composed of organised interests or affected groups who meet periodically to discuss proposals, review evidence, and contribute to decision-making processes. Unlike one-off consultations, stakeholder panels are designed as sustained dialogue forums. They allow institutions to engage actors with specific expertise, responsibilities, or interests in a structured and transparent manner. The OECD emphasises that institutionalised participatory mechanisms can strengthen legitimacy and improve the quality of public decisions, particularly in complex policy areas requiring continuous stakeholder input. Similarly, the Council of Europe’s Code of Good Practice for Civil Participation identifies “dialogue” and “partnership” as higher levels of participation, where public authorities and civil society organisations engage in structured, ongoing interaction. In Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and water governance contexts, stakeholder panels are particularly relevant where multiple actors—such as local authorities, water utilities, environmental NGOs, landowners, researchers, and community representatives—must coordinate across ecological and social dimensions. The IUCN Global Standard for NBS highlights inclusive governance and multi-stakeholder engagement as core requirements for effective NBS implementation. Stakeholder Panels provide a formal mechanism to operationalise this requirement through continuous exchange and co-reflection.

Conditions for implementation

For stakeholder panels to function effectively, several conditions must be met. First, composition must be clearly defined and balanced. Panel membership should reflect the diversity of relevant stakeholder categories, including public authorities, civil society, private sector actors, and affected community representatives. The IAP2 Spectrum emphasises the importance of clarity about the level of influence granted to participants. Therefore, the mandate of the panel - advisory, consultative, or co-decisional - must be explicitly communicated from the outset. Second, terms of reference and governance rules must be established. These should clarify the purpose of the panel, the scope of discussion, the frequency of the meetings, the decision-making or advisory procedures, and the reporting and feedback mechanisms. The Council of Europe stresses that dialogue mechanisms require transparency, mutual respect, and clarity regarding how inputs will be considered. Third, institutional commitment is essential. OECD notes that participatory mechanisms contribute to legitimacy only when authorities demonstrate

responsiveness. Stakeholder Panels must therefore be embedded within formal governance processes, with clear channels for translating panel recommendations into policy or project adjustments.

Process and development phases

Stakeholder Panels generally follow a structured process composed of the following phases. The first phase consists of the identification and selection of the stakeholders, and the relevant actors are mapped and invited based on predefined criteria (sector, expertise, representation, territorial relevance). Selection procedures should be transparent to avoid perceptions of bias. In the second phase, the mandate and working framework are defined: a written mandate or terms of reference is agreed upon, specifying objectives, roles, responsibilities, and expected outputs. The third phase consists of regular deliberative meetings. Meetings are organised at defined intervals, and the sessions may include: the presentation of project updates or technical information, a structured discussion or thematic working groups, and the collection of written or verbal recommendations. The fourth phase is focused on the documentation and feedback loop: meeting minutes, recommendations, and follow-up actions are documented and shared. Authorities or project leaders provide feedback on how panel inputs are integrated. The final phase is monitoring and reviewing. The functioning of the panel is periodically reviewed to assess representativeness, effectiveness, and alignment with project phases. In NBS implementation processes, UNaLab highlights the importance of iterative engagement and structured feedback mechanisms to ensure that stakeholder contributions inform design, implementation, and monitoring stages.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA's participatory governance initiatives emphasise that structured stakeholder dialogue platforms are most effective

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools commonly used within stakeholder panels include:

- Formal meeting agendas and structured discussion formats
- Thematic working groups for specific technical issues
- Evidence briefings and expert presentations to support informed dialogue
- Written consultation rounds on draft documents
- Digital platforms for document sharing and asynchronous feedback

In environmental governance contexts, panels may also use monitoring dashboards, ecological indicators, or performance reports to facilitate evidence-based discussion.

Expected outcomes

Stakeholder Panels produce several tangible and intangible outcomes. Tangible outputs include:

- Written recommendations or advisory opinions
- Structured feedback on draft policies or NBS designs
- Identification of risks, trade-offs, or implementation barriers

Intangible outcomes include:

- Increased transparency
- Strengthened coordination among actors
- Improved trust between institutions and organised stakeholders

when roles and expectations are clearly defined and when outcomes are formally linked to policy cycles. ALDA experiences show that continuity, transparent communication, and follow-up reporting are critical to maintaining engagement and avoiding consultation fatigue.

OECD underscores that sustained engagement mechanisms can contribute to reinforcing trust in democratic institutions when participation is meaningful and responsive. In NBS and water governance, stakeholder panels help align ecological objectives with sectoral interests and local realities, supporting long-term implementation.

3.2.11 World Café

World Café

Method overview and rationale

The World Café is a structured conversational process designed to facilitate open and creative dialogue among large groups of participants. According to Involve, the method enables participants to rotate between small-group discussions organised around specific questions, allowing ideas to circulate and build progressively across tables. The approach is based on the principle that collective intelligence emerges through structured conversation in an informal but purposefully designed setting. Participants typically engage in several rounds of discussion, each focused on a key question, with one person remaining at each table as a “host” to summarise previous conversations for incoming participants. The method is particularly suited to exploratory and generative phases of policy or project development. It does not aim to produce binding decisions but rather to surface diverse perspectives, identify shared concerns, and generate ideas. Within participatory governance frameworks, it corresponds to consultative and dialogic forms of engagement. In the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and water governance, the World Café is relevant during early stages of co-design or strategic reflection, where multiple stakeholders must articulate priorities, expectations, and concerns related to environmental interventions.

Conditions for implementation

Effective World Café processes require careful design and facilitation. First, a clear purpose and well-formulated guiding questions must be established. The quality of the outcomes depends directly on the clarity and relevance of the questions posed. Second, group composition should encourage diversity of perspectives. Participants may include citizens, experts, public officials, and other stakeholders, depending on the objective. Third, facilitation must ensure smooth transitions between discussion rounds. Table hosts should be briefed to summarise previous conversations accurately and neutrally. Fourth, the physical or virtual setting should encourage open dialogue. The World Café traditionally relies on small tables, informal seating arrangements, and visible recording tools to foster engagement. Fifth, documentation mechanisms must be prepared. Table notes, visual mapping, and plenary summaries are necessary to synthesise outcomes.

Process and development phases

The World Café generally follows a structured sequence. A first preparatory phase initiates the process with the definition of the objectives, the development of 2-4 key guiding questions, the organisation of space and materials, and the selection and briefing

Tools and supporting instruments

Operational tools typically include:

- Clearly formulated guiding questions
- Flipcharts or table paper for visual note-taking
- Markers and visual mapping tools

of the table hosts. A first discussion round follows, during which participants are divided into small groups, each group discusses the first question for a defined period, and the key points are recorded at each table. Afterwards, the rotation phase takes place: the participants move to new tables, while the table hosts remain and summarise previous discussions, so that new conversations can build upon earlier contributions. A free number of subsequent rounds can follow, according to the needs, during which additional questions are explored and ideas evolve cumulatively. The process ends with a plenary synthesis session, when key insights are shared with the full group and the facilitators summarise emerging themes and patterns. In NBS and water governance processes, this format can be used to explore thematic dimensions such as ecological priorities, social impacts, governance challenges, and monitoring approaches.

Practice-based insights from ALDA

ALDA publications emphasise interactive dialogue formats and small-group discussions as effective tools for fostering inclusive participation and collective reflection. Similar rotating discussion models are frequently used in participatory workshops to gather diverse perspectives and build shared understanding before moving toward structured decision-making. ALDA experience highlights the importance of clear documentation and feedback mechanisms to ensure that outputs from conversational formats are translated into actionable follow-up steps.

- Timekeeping and facilitation scripts
 - Synthesis templates to structure final reporting
- In environmental contexts, maps, visual representations of proposed interventions, or ecosystem diagrams may be used as discussion prompts.

Expected outcomes

The World Café produces collective insights rather than formal decisions. Tangible outputs include:

- Thematic summaries of ideas
- Identification of shared priorities or concerns
- Clusters of proposals or innovative suggestions

The method also generates relational outcomes, including strengthened dialogue, increased mutual understanding, and expanded networks among participants.

While not producing binding recommendations, the synthesis generated during the plenary phase can inform subsequent planning stages or feed into more structured deliberative processes.

4 Starting conditions of the pilot regions based on D2.1 findings

In this chapter, we report some contextual information about the different project sites involved in the GENESIS project based on D2.1 findings. Such contextual information is useful to allow the identification of the participatory methods suitable in each different setting. It is worth mentioning that D2.1 revealed significant differences in stakeholder readiness in terms of implementation of NBS, economic and institutional capacity, public awareness, engagement cultures and other dimensions across the GENESIS pilot sites (see Table 8.1 of D2.1). As it will be expanded upon in the next chapter, some of these elements are considered crucial for the identification of the methods that suit each site best. In particular, as already mentioned in paragraph 2.2, the following dimensions - together with their related explanations resulting from the analysis conducted in D2.1 - were considered: economic capacity, institutional capacity and public awareness.

4.1 Cape Verde

Cape Verde is characterised by extreme water scarcity and recurrent drought, identified as the dominant water challenge in the comparative assessment. Environmental pressures include limited freshwater availability, erosion and land degradation, which explain why priority NBS types for the region include soil retention, erosion control and traditional water management systems. The environmental context is therefore closely linked to climate vulnerability and fragile water-land systems.

In terms of economic capacity, Cape Verde is classified as Low. The report indicates that financial and resource limitations are the most critical barrier across regions, with Cape Verde showing the highest level of concern (70% of respondents identifying finances as a critical barrier). Small-island economies are described as operating under constrained public budgets where immediate infrastructure or service needs take precedence over long-term ecological investments. In Cape Verde, this structural fiscal limitation directly constrains the scale and speed of NBS implementation.

Regarding institutional capacity, Cape Verde is categorised as Low (capacity constraints). Across regions, limited technical capacity, institutional bottlenecks and regulatory challenges are identified as primary barriers, and these constraints are particularly pronounced in Cape Verde due to restricted administrative resources and limited technical expertise. Governance frameworks are described as evolving, indicating that institutional arrangements are still consolidating and require strengthening to support structured NBS implementation.

Public awareness in Cape Verde is described as Moderate and pragmatic, with a strong focus on immediate water challenges. Survey results indicate conceptual support for NBS and recognition of their relevance to addressing water scarcity. However, perception is strongly performance-oriented: stakeholders emphasise the need for visible, tangible outcomes in order to maintain confidence. Interview findings highlight that NBS are more readily accepted when they are clearly linked to local realities and demonstrated through

pilot initiatives. Financial feasibility remains a major concern in public perception, influencing how NBS are evaluated in terms of practicality and sustainability. Overall, awareness is present and supportive but closely connected to expectations of effectiveness and affordability.

Stakeholder engagement in Cape Verde includes water authorities, municipal administrations, farmers' associations, NGOs, academia and technical experts. In Cape Verde, stakeholder influence is closely tied to access to financial resources, technical expertise and external support mechanisms. Interview evidence underlined the importance of trust-building and early project visibility to sustain engagement.

Overall, the situation in Cape Verde is characterised by strong conceptual openness to NBS combined with severe economic and institutional constraints. Financial limitations, technical capacity gaps and the need for demonstrable local benefits define the implementation context more strongly than social resistance or lack of awareness.

4.2 El Hierro (Canary Islands)

El Hierro is characterised by structural water scarcity within a broader regional context affected by aquifer pressures and climate variability. The environmental setting combines rural, water-dependent areas with recharge zones and higher-altitude reforestation areas identified as suitable for NBS interventions. Proposed areas for application include El Pinar (rural and water-scarce), Pozo de los Padrones recharge zone, and reforestation zones at higher elevations. The island context reflects both ecological vulnerability and dependency on local water resources for primary sector activities.

In terms of economic capacity, El Hierro operates within the Canary Islands context, classified as Moderate. While the region benefits from EU membership and structured public administration, financial constraints remain significant. Across the Canary Islands, 54% of respondents identified financial limitations as a concern. This indicates that although baseline economic capacity is stronger than in non-EU contexts, allocation of resources and prioritisation still condition NBS implementation.

Regarding institutional capacity, the Canary Islands are classified as High due to the presence of established water authorities and technical expertise. However, the report highlights institutional fragmentation and bureaucratic complexity as operational challenges. In El Hierro specifically, interviewees emphasised excessive bureaucracy, limited local pilot examples, and a cultural bias towards "hard" infrastructure. Only one governmental stakeholder reported direct experience with NBS, primarily through compensatory reforestation measures. Other sectoral actors lacked hands-on experience but expressed interest in future pilot projects. Institutional capacity is therefore structurally strong but uneven in practical NBS experience at the local level.

Public awareness in El Hierro is described as limited in practice. While stakeholders understand NBS conceptually as ecosystem-based approaches to water management, interviews indicate low levels of public and political understanding. Some participants noted a generational disconnection regarding water scarcity awareness. At the same time, stakeholders demonstrated recognition of potential benefits, including long-term sustainability, landscape conservation (linked to tourism), reduction of external

dependency, and compatibility with traditional systems. Perception of NBS is therefore cautiously positive among informed actors, but broader public awareness remains underdeveloped and influenced by a preference for conventional infrastructure solutions.

Stakeholder composition in El Hierro includes representatives from renewable energy operations, the dairy livestock sector, and public administration. Stakeholder perspectives within interviews and surveys conducted in T2.1 converged on the need for governance reform, demonstration projects and stronger local engagement. Divergence emerged regarding perceived readiness: some actors viewed the population as supportive in principle, while others highlighted cultural resistance and limited agency.

Overall, the situation in El Hierro is characterised by structurally strong institutional conditions combined with practical experience gaps and limited public awareness. Economic conditions allow potential implementation, but bureaucracy, limited pilot precedents and cultural preference for conventional infrastructure constrain rapid uptake. Support among key actors exists, yet broader societal readiness requires strengthening through education and demonstration.

4.3 Faial (Azores)

Faial, within the Azores archipelago, is situated in a context shaped by climate-related pressures affecting water retention and ecosystem stability. The comparative assessment identifies climate impacts and loss of natural water retention capacity as key challenges. In this setting, NBS priorities include reforestation, wetland restoration and landscape-based interventions aimed at improving infiltration and groundwater recharge. The environmental context combines ecological sensitivity with opportunities for restoration-oriented approaches grounded in landscape management traditions.

Concerning economic capacity, the Azores are classified as Moderate-High. As an EU outermost region, Faial operates within a framework that provides access to European funding instruments and structured public administration. Nevertheless, financial limitations are not absent: 52% of respondents across the Azores identified economic constraints as a relevant barrier. This suggests that while baseline fiscal capacity is comparatively favourable, investment decisions and budget prioritisation still influence the pace and scale of NBS deployment.

With regard to institutional capacity, the Azores are assessed as Moderate. Governance structures are described as cohesive at the regional level, which reduces fragmentation and facilitates coordination. However, the report highlights limited experience with specific technical applications, particularly Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR). Institutional maturity is therefore present, but specialised expertise and technical implementation pathways require further strengthening to enable broader adoption of certain NBS types.

Public awareness in Faial is characterised as High, associated with a strong environmental identity. Survey findings indicate substantial familiarity with NBS concepts and a generally positive perception of their environmental co-benefits and long-term sustainability value. Respondents demonstrate concern about water-related challenges and recognise the relevance of ecosystem-based solutions. Perception is largely supportive and value-driven rather than purely utilitarian. Financial feasibility remains a consideration, but public

attitudes reflect an established environmental consciousness that provides a favourable social basis for implementation.

Stakeholder composition in Faial includes regional public authorities, water management entities, technical and geological institutes, agricultural actors and civil society organisations. The institutional context is described as socially cohesive, with strong social capital supporting participatory approaches. Stakeholders demonstrate awareness of environmental challenges and show readiness to engage in collaborative management models. At the same time, technical specialists play a key role in advancing more complex NBS applications, given the identified gaps in specific expertise, such as MAR.

Overall, the situation in Faial is marked by high environmental awareness and relatively favourable economic conditions, combined with moderate institutional capacity that requires targeted technical reinforcement. The enabling environment is socially supportive, and constraints relate more to specialised expertise and financial prioritisation than to public scepticism.

4.4 Gran Canaria (Canary Islands)

Gran Canaria operates within a regional context marked by aquifer overexploitation and increasing pressure on groundwater resources. The comparative assessment identifies aquifer stress as a dominant water challenge, and priority NBS types include Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) and infiltration basins. The environmental context is therefore characterised by intensive water use, structural groundwater dependency and the need to restore or enhance recharge capacity under climate variability.

In terms of economic capacity, the Canary Islands are classified as Moderate. As an EU outermost region, Gran Canaria benefits from access to European funding mechanisms and structured administrative frameworks. However, financial constraints remain a relevant implementation barrier, with 54% of respondents in the Canary Islands identifying financial limitations as a concern. This indicates that while macro-level economic conditions are comparatively stable, NBS implementation competes with other infrastructural priorities, particularly conventional water infrastructure.

Regarding institutional capacity, the Canary Islands are classified as High, reflecting the presence of established water authorities and technical expertise. In Gran Canaria, interview findings highlight a technically sophisticated water management environment. At the same time, institutional fragmentation and coordination challenges across multiple agencies are identified in the broader regional synthesis. The presence of strong technical institutions does not automatically translate into streamlined NBS implementation, as sectoral structures and bureaucratic complexity influence decision-making processes.

Public awareness in Gran Canaria is described as Variable within the Canary Islands context, partly reflecting urban-rural differences. Survey results show generally high familiarity with NBS and strong concern regarding water-related challenges, particularly loss of natural water retention areas and climate change impacts. Respondents associate NBS with environmental friendliness and multifunctionality. Perception of NBS is broadly positive, though some uncertainty remains regarding cost-effectiveness and maintenance

requirements. Public attitudes therefore combine environmental support with pragmatic considerations about feasibility and long-term management.

Stakeholder composition in Gran Canaria includes regional water authorities, technical professionals, public administration representatives and sectoral actors involved in groundwater management. Interviews indicate that stakeholders possess technical familiarity with water management practices, including recharge-related interventions. Influence within the pilot is shaped by institutional mandates, regulatory authority and sectoral responsibilities. Coordination among multiple agencies is a central operational issue, and multi-stakeholder platforms are identified as relevant mechanisms to address fragmentation.

Overall, the situation in Gran Canaria is characterised by strong technical and institutional foundations combined with moderate economic constraints and coordination challenges. Public perception of NBS is generally favourable, but practical considerations related to cost and implementation complexity shape the pace of adoption. Institutional fragmentation, rather than lack of awareness, represents the principal structural constraint.

4.5 La Palma (Canary Islands)

La Palma is situated within the Canary Islands context, characterised by structural pressure on groundwater resources and increasing exposure to climate-related variability. The broader regional assessment identifies aquifer overexploitation as a key challenge, and this condition also shapes the water management context of La Palma. The island combines rural agricultural areas, recharge zones and ecologically sensitive landscapes where water retention and infiltration are critical. Priority NBS types in the Canary Islands include Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) and infiltration-based measures, reflecting the need to stabilise groundwater systems and enhance recharge capacity.

With regard to economic capacity, La Palma operates within the Moderate classification assigned to the Canary Islands. As an EU outermost region, the island benefits from access to structured public administration and European funding mechanisms. However, financial constraints remain significant, with more than half of respondents in the Canary Islands identifying finances as a barrier. This indicates that while macroeconomic conditions are comparatively stable, budget allocation and competition with conventional infrastructure investments influence NBS feasibility.

In terms of institutional capacity, the Canary Islands are classified as High, reflecting established water authorities and technical competence. In La Palma, interview findings point to institutional and regulatory complexity, as well as coordination challenges among responsible bodies. While technical understanding of water management is present, practical experience with specific NBS applications varies. The SWOT analysis for La Palma highlights both opportunities for water storage enhancement through NBS and weaknesses linked to institutional bottlenecks and administrative procedures. Institutional capacity is therefore structurally strong but operationally affected by fragmentation and procedural constraints.

Public awareness in La Palma follows the broader Canary Islands pattern, described as Variable due to differences between urban and rural contexts. Survey findings indicate familiarity with NBS and recognition of their environmental co-benefits. Respondents associate NBS with sustainability and climate adaptation potential. At the same time, perceptions are influenced by concerns regarding maintenance, long-term effectiveness and cost-efficiency. Attitudes toward NBS are generally positive, but expectations regarding technical performance and financial viability shape how these solutions are evaluated in practice.

Stakeholder composition in La Palma includes representatives from public administration, water management authorities and sectoral actors connected to agriculture and land use. Interview data indicate that stakeholders recognise the relevance of NBS for improving water storage and resilience, yet emphasise the need for clearer regulatory pathways and administrative coordination. Influence within the island is closely linked to institutional mandates and sectoral responsibilities, with governance procedures playing a decisive role in determining implementation speed and scope.

Overall, the situation in La Palma is characterised by technically capable institutions operating within a moderately resourced economic framework, combined with a positive but pragmatically conditioned public perception of NBS. Structural institutional procedures and financial considerations, rather than lack of awareness, represent the main factors shaping implementation dynamics.

4.6 Madeira

Madeira is characterised by seasonal water scarcity and increasing pressure on water availability linked to climatic variability. The comparative assessment identifies seasonal water stress as the dominant water challenge in the region. In this context, priority NBS types include rainwater harvesting and infiltration-based measures aimed at enhancing water retention and local storage capacity. The environmental setting combines steep terrain, agricultural use and water dependency, making distributed retention and storage solutions particularly relevant.

With respect to economic capacity, Madeira is classified as Moderate-High. As an EU outermost region, Madeira benefits from access to European funding instruments and structured regional administration. Nevertheless, financial constraints remain a significant concern, with 69% of respondents identifying finances as a critical barrier - one of the highest levels recorded among the regions. This indicates that although macroeconomic conditions provide relative stability, fiscal prioritisation and resource allocation strongly influence the practical feasibility of NBS investments.

Regarding institutional capacity, Madeira is assessed as Moderate-High, described as strong at the regional level but weaker at the municipal level. The report indicates that while governance structures exist and institutional maturity is present, capacity gaps at the local level affect implementation dynamics. Institutional coordination between regional and municipal authorities is therefore a defining feature of the governance landscape. Technical competence is present, but uneven administrative capacity influences execution and scaling potential.

Public awareness in Madeira is described as Moderate-High and drought-driven. Survey findings show recognition of water scarcity as a pressing issue and acknowledgement of the potential role of NBS in addressing these challenges. Respondents demonstrate positive attitudes toward environmental sustainability and long-term resilience. However, as in other regions, perceptions are influenced by financial feasibility and maintenance considerations. Awareness is therefore shaped by direct experience with drought conditions, and support for NBS is closely linked to their perceived effectiveness in enhancing water security.

Stakeholder composition in Madeira includes regional authorities, municipal administrations, water management bodies and sectoral actors connected to land use and agriculture. The governance setting reflects interaction between regional strategic planning and municipal-level implementation. Stakeholders recognise the need to strengthen municipal capacity and improve coordination across governance levels. Influence within the pilot is therefore structured along regional-local institutional relationships, with implementation dependent on administrative coherence and resource mobilisation. Two major peculiarities of the island's societal composition, which emerged during the performance of the activities later described in Chapter 6 can be identified. On one hand, the island is characterised by a strong tourist presence: in 2024, Madeira recorded around 2.2 million guests in tourist accommodation, indicating significant seasonal inflows compared with its relatively small resident population of approximately 260,000 inhabitants, and reflecting a persistent tourism pressure on local life and services (DREM 2024)²⁵. On the other hand, the region's demographic profile shows a notable presence of foreign residents, with about 5.5 % of the population in Madeira born outside Portugal as of late 2023 and the foreign resident population at a record high of around 14,060 persons (Wikipedia 2023)²⁶. Madeira also faces an ageing population dynamic, with the proportion of elderly residents (65 years and over) increasing over time and an ageing ratio that continues to grow relative to younger cohorts, consistent with broader EU trends towards higher shares of older individuals across regions (Eurostat 2026)²⁷. This combination of high tourism intensity, a growing foreign resident share and a rising elderly population poses evident challenges as these stakeholder groups can prove complex to actively engage, especially on scientific, technical issues related to climate change and Nature-based Solutions. Senior residents or long-term migrants may have distinct participation behaviours, time availability and priorities that require tailored engagement approaches to ensure meaningful involvement.

Overall, the situation in Madeira is characterised by relatively favourable economic and institutional conditions combined with pronounced financial constraints and coordination challenges at the municipal level. Public perception of NBS is generally supportive and strongly shaped by the lived experience of water scarcity, while implementation feasibility depends on strengthening local administrative capacity and securing financial resources.

²⁵ [Direção Regional de Estatística da Madeira \(DREM\), n.d. Press release section.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026) and [DREM Official Statistics Website n.d. Resident population of the Autonomous Region of Madeira exceeded 256,000 persons, recording the largest increase in the last five years.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

²⁶ [Wikipedia \(updated on 24 February 2026\). Madeira.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026)

²⁷ [Eurostat \(2026\). Population on 1 January by age group, sex and country of birth. \[Data set\]. Eurostat and Eurostat \(updated on 2 February 2026\). Population structure and ageing.](#) (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

5 Pilot-specific methods for public engagement and dialogue

In order to proceed with the identification of the methods most suitable for each implementing project site, the features of the different sites were analysed according to key dimensions identified in D2.1 and reported in paragraph 2.2. To enable the matching exercise, the same dimensions were also applied to the eleven methodologies identified in Chapter 3, considering them also good parameters to assess the applicability of the different methodologies in the different contexts.

For each participatory method identified, different levels of the above-listed dimensions are required to ensure its concrete applicability.

The following table reports the analysis conducted to assess the different participatory methods along the three dimensions listed. It is worth highlighting that all the methodologies presented require a multistakeholder approach for their successful implementation and results.

Table 2. Comparative summary table of the expected levels of the three dimensions (economic capacity, institutional capacity and public awareness) per each participatory method

Method	Expected economic capacity level for its implementation	Expected institutional capacity level for its implementation	Expected public awareness level for its implementation
Citizen Assembly	High (large groups, multiple sessions, participant compensation, facilitation)	High (strong administrative coordination, credible institutional commitment, technical expertise)	Medium - high (participants engage with complex information and deliberation; basic environmental awareness improves quality of outcomes)
Citizen Forum	Medium-high (significant organisational investment)	High (multi-stakeholder, policy makers directly involved)	Medium (in-depth dialogue, interaction with experts)
Citizen Jury	Medium (smaller groups and shorter duration)	Medium-high (structure design required, expert hearings and formal)	Medium (structured information to jurors, but basic)

		response mechanisms)	understanding helps deliberation)
Community Visioning	Medium (multiple workshops, facilitation, communication, moderate costs)	Medium (coordination and planning capacity)	Medium (participants able to reflect on long-term community challenges and opportunities)
Consensus Conference	High (expert hearing, facilitation, multiple sessions)	High (independent organising body, structured procedures)	Medium-high (participants engaged with technical information and structured deliberation)
Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches	Low-medium (modest resources, although some formats can increase costs)	Low-medium (small teams or community groups)	Low (more awareness-raising tools, no prior knowledge required)
Deliberative Workshop	Medium (facilitation, materials, one or a few sessions)	Medium (facilitation capacity and basic coordination)	Medium (some familiarity with the topic recommended)
Focus Group	Low (small groups, short sessions, limited logistics)	Low (minimal administrative capacity)	Low (designed to gather perceptions even where awareness is limited)
Living Lab	High (pilot projects, monitoring, coordination)	High (multi-actor partnerships, governance structure, long-term institutional support)	Medium (engagement in co-design, with no high prior knowledge required)

Stakeholder panel	Medium (repeated meetings, coordination, facilitation, but limited participants)	Medium-high (clear mandates, terms of reference, integration into governance cycles)	Medium (participants usually stakeholders with basic knowledge or interest in the topic)
World Cafè	Low (minimal materials and short duration)	Low-medium (basic organisational capacity and facilitation)	Low-medium (conversational and exploratory method)

Based on the pilot sites' description presented in Chapter 4, as well as the methods' assessment around the three dimensions identified above, the following matching exercise has been conducted, with the purpose to identify the methods most suitable in each context.

Table 3. Overview of the methods and pilots matching exercise according to the three selected dimensions

Method	Madeira	Canary Islands (La Palma, Gran Canaria)	El Hierro	Faial (Azores)	Cape Verde
Citizen Assembly	X				
Citizen Forum		X			
Citizen Jury	X	X		X	
Community Visioning	X	X		X	

Consensus Conference	X				
Creative and Cultural Participatory Approaches			X		X
Deliberative Workshop	X	X		X	
Focus Group			X		X
Living Lab	X				
Stakeholder panel	X			X	
World Cafè			X		X

The table above shows that more sophisticated methodologies, such as citizen juries, community visioning, and deliberative workshops, are particularly suitable for locations like Madeira, the Canary Islands, and Faial, which are characterised by moderate to high levels of economic and institutional capacity, as well as public awareness. Conversely, less complex methods such as focus groups, world café, and creative and cultural participatory approaches, although in principle applicable in all locations, are more appropriate for sites like El Hierro and Cape Verde, which display lower levels of economic and institutional capacity and public awareness. It is important to emphasise that the proposed matching does not, in principle, prevent the different sites from implementing methodologies other than those identified as most suitable. The matching exercise is intended to indicate ideal alignment conditions and does not imply that the implementation of alternative methodologies would necessarily be unsuccessful.

In particular, as far as the island of Faial (Azores) is concerned, methodologies such as community visioning, citizen juries, stakeholder panels, and deliberative workshops - which build on existing social capital and trust-based relationships - are especially appropriate.

Indeed, the Azores' combination of social capital, environmental awareness, and functional institutional structures makes them well suited to participatory processes that emphasise co-creation, shared territorial vision, and iterative experimentation, rather than highly resource-intensive national-scale deliberative mechanisms.

Similarly, the Canary Islands combine strong willingness to engage, a well-established participatory culture, and certain institutional coordination challenges. This suggests prioritising methodologies that integrate structured deliberation, multi-actor alignment, and visible pilot experimentation in order to translate this readiness into effective and coherent NBS governance outcomes. Suitable methodologies include citizen forums, citizen juries, community visioning, and deliberative workshops. The absence of the Citizen Assembly and Living Lab methodologies among those considered most suitable for the Canary Islands setting (including La Palma) - although indicated in the project Grant Agreement - is due to the fact that both methodologies ideally require high levels of economic and institutional capacity, as well as medium to high public awareness. While the Canary Islands are characterised by strong institutional capacity, they display only moderate economic capacity and variable levels of public awareness. This situation does not prevent their implementation, since, as stated above, the matching exercise is intended to indicate ideal alignment conditions and does not imply that the implementation of alternative methodologies would necessarily be unsuccessful.

Madeira's combination of institutional stability, available capacity, and environmental awareness makes it one of the pilot territories most suited to advanced deliberative and co-creative methodologies, particularly those capable of generating formal recommendations and structured outputs, and supporting governance innovation. These include citizen assemblies, citizen juries, community visioning, consensus conferences, deliberative workshops, living labs, and stakeholder panels. In Chapter 6.1, the case of Madeira's citizen assembly turning into a stakeholder panel is analysed.

By contrast, both Cape Verde and El Hierro are characterised by resource constraints, evolving institutional frameworks, and relatively low levels of public awareness, shaped by lived experiences of water scarcity and climate vulnerability, as well as limited environmental education. In these contexts, it is advisable to prioritise trust-building, dialogue-oriented, and experiential methodologies capable of gradually reinforcing governance capacity while ensuring broad-based participation, such as focus groups, world café, and creative and cultural participatory approaches.

6 Public engagement activities in the project's sites

As foreseen by Task 2.2 of the GENESIS project, this deliverable is drafted to provide guidance and insights on innovative social engagement approaches, participatory methodologies, communication tools, formats and styles that are most effective for mainstreaming NBS and innovative water management approaches in Macaronesia. At the time of the release of this deliverable, two out of the nine demonstrator sites proved ready to perform citizen and stakeholder engagement activities: La Palma and Madeira.

Below, an exhaustive description of the two events is provided, starting from the preliminary actions taken, the adopted approach/method and the results and conclusions drawn. It is worth anticipating that the two case studies provide opposite yet complementary examples, with Madeira proving less effective than La Palma. This allows us to pinpoint best practices, relevant preliminary conditions and effective follow-up actions, useful for future activities in the other pilots and for replication purposes.

6.1 Case study 1: Madeira (Portugal) Citizen Assembly

The GENESIS project partner, the University of Madeira (UMa), was responsible for conducting the project's first citizen and stakeholder engagement activity. It was decided to organise the activity concurrently with the GENESIS Consortium annual meeting in order to take advantage of the presence of project partners. The engagement activity, designed as a Citizen Assembly, was held on 7 October 2025 in Funchal (Madeira, Portugal). The following section provides an overview of the process followed and of the activity implemented, based on the report prepared by UMa and included as Annex 2.

6.1.1 Preliminary work

The activity was designed on the basis of the documents provided by ALDA (a comprehensive guide on how to perform Citizen Assemblies), and in alignment with GENESIS's key goal to enhance climate resilience of critical water infrastructures, while also promoting civic engagement and combining it with innovation and science. It is worth highlighting that the project partner UMa followed a rather autonomous approach in implementing a revised version of the Citizen Assembly methodology based on its needs, and the process involved only sporadic communications with ALDA and the rest of the Consortium.

As part of the preliminary work, UMa identified the target audience (focusing mainly on stakeholders who had a relevance to water management challenges in Madeira) and the speakers. The latter were chosen on the basis of the following three main criteria: their institutional relevance and leadership, their scientific authority and role in the GENESIS project coordination, and the degree of their stakeholders' representativeness. Furthermore, the choice of the location was made on the basis of the engagement needs of the activity: Funchal, the capital of Madeira, ensures easy access for regional

GENESIS - D2.2 Guidelines for public engagement and dialogue authorities, stakeholders, and citizens, and the University itself provides institutional legitimacy while being, at the same time, a neutral and accessible venue.

6.1.2 Implementation

The event was advertised by various GENESIS partners on social media and through university email stakeholder contacts. The activity took place in one of the rooms of the University of Madeira and consisted of a 1-hour panel discussion, included in the first day of the agenda of GENESIS' Consortium General Assembly. The project was introduced and discussed, and this was followed by a stakeholder roundtable and an open Q&A session.

The detailed agenda of the event was shared in advance with the registered participants and reported the following information (the original agenda document is attached as Annex 1):

Table 4. Overview of the Citizen Assembly organised in Madeira on October 7th, 2025

Event detail	Description
Title	Citizen Assembly
Date	7 th October 2025
Duration	2 hours
Language	Portuguese
Location	University of MADERIA, R. dos Ferreiros Estrada, São Martinho, 9000-082 Funchal, Portugal
Target audience	90 (target) diverse stakeholders; General public, community leaders, local businesses, water stakeholders
Organisers	Eduardo Leite and Yasmine Challouf (UMa)

In particular, the speakers touched on the following points: the GENESIS project and its climate adaptation strategy; the role of Nature-based Solutions in strengthening water resilience; Madeira's specific challenges, including seasonal water demand, infrastructure vulnerability, and climate risks; the importance of citizen participation and local cooperation for successful implementation.

The following discussion was quite meaningful, and stakeholders shared practical insights from their sectors, identifying key issues and potential opportunities for improvement. The event concluded with ending remarks, but no refreshment or networking session was envisaged for the participants (besides the GENESIS Consortium partners).

The activity saw the attendance of approximately 20 participants, including GENESIS project partners, water management and environmental experts, representatives of academic and research institutions, agricultural and sectoral representatives and civil society actors and citizens. The event was gender balanced but did not foresee characteristics to be fully inclusive (for instance, no language interpreters were foreseen).

All in all, the activity helped strengthen dialogue between scientists, authorities, and citizens and increased awareness of climate risks and Nature-based Solutions, with a specific focus on Macaronesia and Madeira.

Table 5. Preliminary agenda of the Citizen Assembly organised in Madeira on October 7th, 2025

Time	Duration (mins)	Activity
14:30	15	Opening session: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and introduction of the organising team (UMA, IGME, ALDA, EFG) • Session objectives and overview of the agenda • Rules of participation: courteous dialogue, appreciation of diverse perspectives • Brief introduction of participants (name and role/connection to local water issues)
14:45	45	Genesis project introduction presentation, given by Vitor Correia (EFG): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the GENESIS project? • Objectives and scope • Explanation of nature-based solutions in accessible language • Project timeline and milestones • Expected results at regional (Macaronesia) and European level
15:00	30	Maderia’s Demonstrator site presentation by Eduardo Leite (Uma) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of the need for the NBS Demo site

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of how the NBS site will function • Expected results of the NBS being proposed
15:30	15	Coffee break
15:45	45	Round Table <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic 1: Local water challenges (15 minutes) • Topic 2: Evaluation of solutions (15 minutes) • Topic 3: Considerations on Implementation (15 min)
16:30	30	Open Question and Answer Session
17:00	15	Conclusion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How community input will be used • Contact information and opportunities for ongoing participation • Acknowledgements and announcement of upcoming sessions

6.1.3 Follow-up activities

After the event, a follow-up email was sent to participants in order to thank them and share with them materials related to the event. No formal written feedback survey was shared with the participants. However, UMA collected various informal feedback during and immediately after the event, and that was majorly positive, with participants expressing interest in the project and appreciation for the open discussion format.

6.1.4 Key challenges and lessons-learnt

The activity was successful and saw the participation of a diverse and engaged group of stakeholders, but it presented various challenges related mainly to organisational aspects and participation.

As for participation, it proved quite hard to meaningfully engage the local community, resulting in a small sized activity. This is likely due to some societal aspects that are common in the Macaronesian islands, and particularly in Madeira, as previously mentioned in Chapter 4, such as an ageing population and strong tourist presence.

Engaging with elderly people can be challenging but possible, and actually meaningful; indeed, as the Grey4Green project (G4G)²⁸ proved, this can be done also on climate change- and environment-related topics. The best way to engage with elderly people is to first raise awareness through clear and reachable communication channels about available activities, that should preferably be local and accessible as this can reduce practical barriers (e.g. mobility). It is also relevant to include in the activities a part of training and guidance, and structured support, since a lack of knowledge and self-confidence often prevent participation, especially in relation to climate issues and technology (e.g. Nature-Based-Solutions). Social interaction, networking, and shared activities are also strong motivators for this group of people, so it would be advisable to consider social, intergenerational activities, especially if the hosting organisation is a school or university.

The Grey4Green findings indicate that engagement methodologies in the Macaronesian pilots should prioritise accessibility, structured facilitation, experiential learning and social motivation, recognising elderly participants as knowledgeable contributors whose participation increases when meaning, safety and community belonging are ensured.

As far as the strong tourist presence is concerned, this offers a limited opportunity of involvement as often tourists lack a long-term view for the territory, thus it would not necessarily be advisable to target them, if the activity aims to create connections and involve citizens in the long-term co-creation of local solutions. At the same time, tourists represent a “transient” social component, which despite its short-term presence, has significant interaction with local systems and services. In the Macaronesian context and Madeira especially, tourists coexist with a structurally different and more stable group: long-term migrants and foreign-born residents who have relocated to the islands for work, lifestyle or retirement reasons and who progressively integrate into local socio-economic systems (Eurostat 2026)²⁹.

Unlike short-stay visitors, long-term immigrant residents (both EU and non-EU) constitute a relevant target group for structured participatory governance. The “IN’ Etterbeek”³⁰ participatory model developed by the municipality of Etterbeek (Brussels, Belgium) demonstrates that municipalities can successfully engage residents of different nationalities through permanent participatory platforms combining assemblies, thematic working groups and co-creation mechanisms open to all registered residents, regardless of citizenship status. This confirms that residency, rather than nationality, can serve as the primary eligibility criterion for inclusion in deliberative and co-decision processes.

Overall, while tourists offer limited continuity for participatory governance, long-term immigrant residents represent a stable and under-utilised constituency. Evidence from Etterbeek shows that inclusive, residency-based participatory frameworks can effectively integrate diverse EU and non-EU populations into structured co-creation processes. Applied to the Macaronesian pilots, such approaches would respond to demographic realities, reinforce social cohesion and strengthen the long-term legitimacy and sustainability of citizen-driven Nature-based Solutions.

²⁸ Grey4Green project (G4G) project website available at <https://grey4green.eu/> (Accessed: 26 February 2026).

²⁹ Eurostat (2026). *Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments - monthly data* [Data set]. Eurostat. (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

³⁰ Etterbeek, *In’Etterbeek*. (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

In relation to organisational insights and tips, for an efficient organisation/planning, effective engagement processes require careful and early planning, with clear timelines, defined tasks, and organised logistical steps to ensure smooth implementation. Structuring activities chronologically and using simple planning tools helps coordinate organisational, administrative, and strategic aspects while maintaining efficiency and accessibility. At the same time, communication should be carefully phased, inclusive, and diversified to build sustained interest and broad participation. This means starting early with awareness-raising, maintaining visibility through reminders, and sharing clear, detailed information through multiple channels and community spaces. Considering the societal components outlined above (tourists, immigrants and elderly), the diversification of the communication activity becomes even more relevant: paper-based communication channels, informal public gathering spaces and community venues (such as restaurants, cultural centres, public squares etc.) (besides digital channels) must be better targeted, since they prove to be the most effective means of information exchange in the Macaronesian context.

A key element to be highlighted is that although the implementation of a Citizen Assembly was initially planned, several practical constraints made it impossible to carry it out as intended. In particular, organizational activities were initiated too close to the scheduled date, preventing effective promotion of the event and resulting in limited participation (only 20 people attended, whereas the expected number for a Citizen Assembly is significantly higher). Consequently, the team decided to convert the event into a panel discussion. The stakeholder panel proved to be interesting and insightful to the participants but provided too little space for interaction, knowledge-exchange and societal engagement. Nevertheless, the case of Madeira is hereby reported as a testimony of general points to keep in mind in the organisation of stakeholders and citizen engagement activities, and of some issues specific for the Macaronesia settings.

6.2 Case study 2: La Palma (Spain) Citizens Water Forum

The event in Madeira partially informed the following one performed in La Palma, which was better adapted according to the findings expressed above and insights collected in that occasion. A Citizen Assembly did not prove the most effective and feasible solution to implement, also considering that other local organisations were organising a citizen assembly in the same period of time, in the frame of a separate event. Therefore, the consortium opted for another format, in order not to antagonise within the controversial space of water management in La Palma: the event in La Palma was constructed as a Citizen Forum on water and NBS and named “Citizen Water Forum”. The Forum proved interesting and insightful to the participants, providing a relevant space for interaction, knowledge-exchange and societal engagement. The present chapter outlines the description of the process carried out for the planning and development of the citizen engagement activity in La Palma. It will delve into the preliminary work conducted, the methodology and structure adopted and its results. The full report of the activity is available in Annex 4.

6.2.1 Preliminary work

A working group formed of multiple partners: AIM, CSIC, ALDA, LPRC, VCPGT, and EFG was created to collaborate in the citizen engagement activities to be conducted in La Palma. Based on the site's features and needs, the structure of a Citizen Water Forum (see paragraph 3.2.2 on Citizen Forums) was considered the most suitable to engage residents in that location. A series of meetings took place among the partners mentioned above in order to agree on the topics, a preliminary agenda, and materials to be provided. Besides the regular meetings, preparatory documents on citizen and stakeholder engagement activities and operational advice were provided by ALDA (GENESIS' partner in charge of providing guidance on such activities) to AIM (GENESIS' partner identified to perform the activity in practice). The need to identify a local, independent consultant firm to assist in the logistics and running of the event was identified, as well as the need to have language interpreters (to facilitate the participation of external partners not fluent in Spanish and hearing-impaired people). In order to ensure broad media coverage, the local TV was invited for the morning introductory and explanatory session. It is worth mentioning that the partners mentioned above, and AIM and ALDA more precisely, maintained constant communication and collaboration throughout the whole process. This collaborative approach and expertise exchange was instrumental in the success of the event.

6.2.2 Implementation

On Friday, 28th November 2025, a preparation session took place. Members of the consortium who would be assisting in the Citizen Water Forum attended. This was an opportunity to explain the event and for clarification of roles, e.g. speaker, note taker, moderator, and supervisor.

The event took place on the 29th November 2025 at the Archaeological Museum Benahoarita (MAB) in La Palma, Spain. 66 people attended (36 men and 30 women). Participants represented a variety of stakeholders spanning from water-related experts belonging to various organisations, climate- and environmental-related stakeholders, and a non-expert audience. The participants who provided information on their sector/profession of origin included people from the public administrations, especially the insular government authorities; from the private sector, namely an environmental and water management consultancy; civil society organisations, especially focused on water management; environmental associations; and an agricultural sector association.

The detailed agenda of the event was shared in advance with the registered participants and reported the following information (the original agenda document is attached as Annex 3):

Table 6. Overview of the Citizens' Water Forum in La Palma on 29th November 2025

Event detail	Description
Title	Citizen Water Forum
Date	29 th November 2025
Duration	5 hours
Language	Spanish (with sign language and English interpretation)
Location	Archaeological museum Benahoarita, C. las Adelfas, 38760 Los Llanos, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Spain
Target audience	90 (target) diverse stakeholders; General public, community leaders, local businesses, water stakeholders
Organiser	Iván Hernández Ríos
Registration	Registration form

Table 7. Agenda of the Citizens' Water Forum in La Palma on 29th November 2025

Time	Duration (mins)	Activity
9:00	45	Registration
09:45	30	Opening: Facilitators welcomed and introduced the audience to the event agenda, objectives, format, and ground rules.
10:15	30	Explanatory session Presentation 1. Alejandro Garcia, IGME, presentation on the need for the Genesis project based on climate change risks. Followed by a Q&A session.
10:45	30	Explanatory Session Presentation 2. Ivan Hernandez, AIM, Presentation on the demonstrator NBS in La Palma and social engagement component. Followed by a Q&A session.
11:15	15	Introduction to the groups: The Facilitator allocated participants to each group and explained the goal of the discussion
11:30	30	Break
12:00	90	Group discussion: Groups discussed the three proposed topics (Climate change, Digitisation, and Decision-making and management).
13:30	30	Plenary Session: Each group presented the results of their discussions.
13:55	5	Conclusions, acknowledgements and last messages from the organisers.
14:00	-	Lunch offered to all participants

A consent document was distributed to all attendees upon arrival to confirm if they were happy for recordings (for internal use only) to be made and photography to be used on social media. Efforts were made to avoid direct pictures of the participants and keep such pictures out of social media postings.

To start the explanatory session, an animated video, commissioned by LRPC before the event, which portrayed an overview of the deep demonstrator on La Palma was played. This had the advantage of being specific to the island of La Palma, engaging, and simple before the presentations added more details.

As detailed in the agenda above, the GENESIS Technical Project Leader held a 30-minute presentation on Nature-Based Solutions and GENESIS project topics, setting the scene. Afterwards, the GENESIS WP4 leader and partner responsible for the Citizen Forum activity took the floor to focus on the demonstration sites of La Palma and the planned social engagement component of the project. It was decided to have two Q&A sessions after each of the two presentations to keep the event interactive and allow the audience to clarify any doubts in a gradual, smooth manner.

During the question and answer sessions, the GENESIS project objectives, background data, and expected outcomes were challenged by two representatives of the Water Association for La Palma (Asociación Aguas Para La Palma)³¹. The Association advocates for transparent and sustainable water governance in La Palma, arguing that the island's water scarcity is largely the result of mismanagement rather than actual shortage. They oppose further desalination investments, promoting instead improved distribution efficiency, aquifer protection, and more sustainable extraction and wastewater treatment practices (more information on their website). Their presence transformed the event into a debate and continuous interlocution between the speakers (project leaders and partners) and the audience, making the event dynamic and interesting. Such an active and pre-structured engagement gave the event a somewhat one-sided and confrontational tone. In the case of replicating the event in other contexts, more informed stakeholders might take the floor, potentially maintaining a confrontational dynamic but broadening the range of topics discussed and perspectives addressed. Another remarkable note was the presence of a public official from the public water authority of the Cabildo La Palma, the General Manager of the La Palma Water Council (Consejo Insular de Aguas de La Palma, CIALP)³², who helped to keep the tone of the discussion collaborative using a diplomatic but authentic language.

Questions from the audience focused on the data used for the performance of project activities and the engagement with the private sector. Leveraging on these questions, GENESIS Leader and the Citizen Forum activity leader clarified that the GENESIS project's core objective is not to influence the political will or decisions but rather to create NBS tools and prove their effectiveness. The expected results are not an immediate modification of water use, but an increased understanding of water flow, forecasting supply and demand, and an empowerment of science-based management of water.

³¹ The website of the organisation Asociación Aguas Para La Palma is accessible at <https://sites.google.com/view/tunel-de-trasvase-la-palma/inicio?authuser=0> and the Facebook page at <https://www.facebook.com/aquaparaalapalma/> (Accessed: 24 February 2026).

³² The webpage of the Consejo Insular de Aguas de La Palma (CIALP) is accessible at <https://lapalmaaguas.com/> (Accessed: 24 February 2026).

The first session lasted for approximately 2 hours and was followed by a break. After such refreshment break, the citizens and staff reconvened in a large open space within the museum. An introduction by the consultants and the representative from ALDA set the tone for the afternoon session, presenting it as an initiative promoting local democracy and explaining that the results of the session would be reported to the EU and made publicly available.

Later, three groups of 10 - 12 citizens each were formed, ensuring gender and age diversity and balance and gathered around large tables to discuss solutions to the water issues in La Palma under the following categories: Climate change, Digitisation, and Decision-making and management. The citizen groups were divided with colours (yellow, blue, and red) to help identify the inputs collected in the reporting phase. Each group had a facilitator and a notaker. The Project Leader, Activity Leader and the General Manager of the La Palma Water Council were not present in the room to avoid influencing the opinions of attendees during the discussion.

Each group reunited around a circular table with a big paper poster in the middle, meant as the final output, gathering all their ideas and discussion topics. The participants were given post-its, pens, and small stickers (for voting purposes). The facilitator first introduced the session and explained the methodology. The activity was divided in three rounds of 30 minutes each to discuss in turn the three overarching topics: Climate change, Digitisation, and Decision-making. During each round, the participants were asked to write one or more of their thoughts related to the topic on a post-it and then put it on the bigger poster at the center for general discussion. The facilitator at the table grouped the collected post-its into different clusters according to the similarity of the ideas written on them. The post-it collection was followed by an open discussion on the specific topics and/or the clusters formed. The debate ended with a voting moment during which participants were asked to express their preference for one of the clusters. Their preference expressed the cluster topic they believed had the most relevance for the overarching topic. This process was repeated for each of the three guiding topics. The notetaker's role was to listen and write down the ideas discussed and everything that was happening in the group. The participants were never pushed to talk or stay at the table. On the contrary, a relaxed and open environment was created to allow for free, informal discussion. Refreshments were also available in the room for this purpose.

The second part of the event lasted around 2 hours, with 1 hour and 30 minutes for the group work and 30 minutes of a plenary session, during which one or more representatives per each group presented their results to everyone in the room. After the final conclusions and thanks, a group picture and joint lunch followed.

The atmosphere remained calm and collaborative in all three groups. In general, the second part of the event had a strong social, collaborative and supportive tone. The role of the facilitators and the notetakers in each group was essential to allow this.

The interactive afternoon session was documented by pictures, paper-based materials used for the activity and digital notes.

The results of each of the three groups are summarised below, while detailed notes are available in Annex 5.

6.2.2.1 Yellow Group

The Yellow group (10 participants) discussed climate change, digitalisation, and decision-making in water management, often agreeing in many respects.

On climate change, discussions focused on irrigation improvements, water-saving culture, infrastructure renewal, forest protection, and reducing water-intensive crops. The top priorities were efficient water capture and distribution and water-saving culture.

Regarding digitalisation, participants stressed the need to adapt technological solutions to La Palma's specific geographical and cultural context. Automation for monitoring and reducing water waste was prioritised, while maintaining a balance between innovation and tradition. The leading cluster was automation systems.

In decision-making, education and citizen awareness emerged as key themes, alongside the need for improved public-private co-governance and updated regulations. Education and citizen action received the most support.

Overall, participants valued the activity for strengthening dialogue and community engagement, while recommending greater inclusion of farmers and older citizens through more accessible outreach channels.

6.2.2.2 Blue Group

The Blue group (12 participants, including two teenagers) engaged in dynamic and collaborative discussions on climate change, digitalisation, and decision-making in water governance.

On climate change, participants emphasised the island's vulnerability and the urgency of reducing water consumption across sectors. Education, awareness-raising, water reuse, rainwater harvesting, and maintenance of existing infrastructure were highlighted as key actions. The most prioritised cluster concerned rainwater harvesting and infrastructure maintenance.

Regarding digitalisation, two main clusters emerged: sensors and remote (telematic) control. Discussions focused on gaps in data collection, monitoring, transparency, and data-sharing, as well as the need for stronger investment in digital tools. Participants also addressed concerns about equitable water accountability, particularly in relation to farmers. The debate was lively, with differing views that ultimately led to consensus-building.

In decision-making, discussions centred on governance models, expert roles, transparency, and the balance between public and private responsibilities. Participants stressed the importance of independent studies, expert-informed decisions, citizen participation, and accessible digital portals providing reliable information. Among the identified priorities, expert-led decisions supported by further studies received the most support.

Overall, despite politically sensitive topics, the group maintained a constructive approach and concluded the session by consolidating shared priorities and key messages for the plenary.

6.2.2.3 Red group

The Red group (12 participants) discussed climate change, digitalisation, and decision-making in water governance, engaging in constructive and at times contrasting debates.

On climate change, four clusters emerged: efficiency, storage, new water sources, and policy. Discussions addressed resistance to change, water storage challenges, privatisation concerns, and the perception of water as a public good. Participants highlighted the importance of shared water data for informed decision-making. Efficiency and storage were prioritised.

Regarding digitalisation, participants focused on water consumption monitoring, data management, and participation. The debate emphasised the need for improved data collection, transparent sharing, and intelligent analysis. Concerns were raised about negative perceptions around data provision and about farmers being disproportionately blamed for water use. The most supported priorities were water consumption monitoring and data management.

In decision-making, two clusters emerged: hydrological planning and citizen and technical participation. Participants called for reduced political influence, stronger expert involvement, early warning systems, and broader citizen engagement through transparent and accessible processes. The most voted priority was citizen and technical participation in decision-making.

Overall, the group positively assessed the activity, valuing it as a productive participatory space and expressing willingness to remain engaged in future water governance processes.

6.2.2.4 Conclusions on the three groups

This citizen involvement exercise proved interesting and useful in many respects. Firstly, the dynamics and the discussion of the group changed according to the people involved, their views and their personal attitude. This is something to keep in mind when organising a similar initiative: the outcome largely depends also on the people involved. Groups with heterogeneous participants collected numerous diversified ideas, which complicated the clustering moment and enriched the discussion; while groups composed of like-minded and/or agreeable people promoted a more harmonious and less debated activity. Moreover, the role of the group moderators and facilitators hired for the overall event was key to keeping the event participative and welcoming for everyone involved. Secondly, although the participants did not share their views until the end of the activity during the plenary session, many similarities emerged in the group discussions. This proves that there are

some core topics which are strongly felt in the community and which raise different beliefs and opinions. These are listed below:

- The importance of societal education, awareness and action for the promotion of a water-saving culture were recognised in both the Yellow and Blue groups. The Red group also tackled this issue, but through the lenses of data transparency, sharing and accessibility to make the society aware of their water consumption and involve them in water-related issues.
- All groups agreed on the lack of sufficient information and clarity on the use of the water resources, especially related to the citizens' consumption records, and the underutilization or misuse of the data, especially in the policy-making realm. In this respect, the Red group mentioned the importance of fighting stereotypes and negative connotations associated with the provision of information by users. This aspect is relevant as it should be included in the point above on societal education.
- All the groups positively evaluated this activity and the collaborative atmosphere which favoured it. They also expressed their interest and the need for more of such participatory opportunities, underlying the added value that they would bring, such as improved democratic governance and social action, and enhanced understanding of environmental and water issues.
- All the groups mentioned the agricultural sector and/or farmers as disproportionately blamed for water use, emphasising that also other sectors and/or economic actors should be accounted as responsible.
- Water accessibility and governance proved to be a debated topic in all groups. On the one hand, some people of the Red group believed that there are no water accessibility issues and rather a general atmosphere of collaboration and willingness to share such resource, while in the Yellow group, people were concerned about the difficulties experienced by citizens living in the most remote areas of the island. On the other hand, both the Yellow and Blue group pointed out the strong need for a more harmonious water co-management between public and private bodies, user communities and owners of water infrastructures.

As mentioned, the notes of the groups are available in Annex 5 for an in-depth read of the discussions, together with some pictures taken during the activity.

6.2.3 Follow-up activities

After the event, follow-up and thank-you emails were sent to the collaborators, acknowledging their involvement in the organisation and development of the conference. These emails also included the photographs taken by professionals during the activity, in order to facilitate their dissemination and documentation.

In terms of informal feedback, during the course of the event, various spontaneous assessments were collected from attendees. Several people highlighted the interest of the content covered and the dynamic nature of the methodology used, noting that the format

facilitated participation and the exchange of perspectives. At the end of the day, the general atmosphere was positive, and there was a sense of satisfaction among participants regarding the event, highlighting the local need for more events of this kind. Interviews were also conducted with both participants and members of the organisation team during the activity, which allowed for additional impressions of the experience to be gathered.

The event was broadcast on the island's television programme *Canarias 2.0*³³, thus extending its reach beyond the audience in attendance. Similarly, posts were made on social media to reinforce the visibility of the activity and help communicate its main results.

6.2.4 Key challenges and lessons-learnt

Unlike the event performed in Madeira, the Citizen Water Forum in La Palma proved more successful for a number of reasons: 1) The operational organisation started well in advance (3 months before the set date) and was supported by a team of partners from the GENESIS project throughout the whole process; 2) Such team carefully considered potential obstacles, opportunities and desired outcomes when planning; 3) The local project partners had a solid network on site which enhanced the organisation and promotion of the event; 4) La Palma is the GENESIS project pilot with the majority of on-site demonstrators and therefore makes it a good example and interesting, concrete topic for the island residents; 5) The local community proved to have basic knowledge of climate change and, especially, of the water situation of the island, and demonstrated will to debate and be involved in it. These conditions allowed for the correct development and satisfactory outcome of the event.

6.3 Case study 3: La Palma Living Lab

It is worth mentioning that the La Palma site has also initiated the implementation of Living Labs within its territory. However, at the time of drafting the present document, no activity report has yet been produced. The outcomes and related activities will therefore be presented in a subsequent document.

For the purpose of this deliverable, it suffices to mention that Living Lab was included as a method to raise awareness on the project, NBS and water-related issues in the project proposal of the GENESIS project. More specifically, a Living Lab is foreseen in La Palma to demonstrate at full scale how NBS can increase the resilience of La Palma's water system across the four demonstrators based on the island (Barlovento, Trásvase, Tenisca and Angustias).

³³ YouTube video on TelevisionCanaria "Canarias 2.0 | 13/12/25" available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=okahb41BNfk> (Accessed: 25 February 2026) and YouTube video on Canarias2Punto0 "PROYECTO GÉNESIS" available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SwYhP7fQnJg> (Accessed: 25 February 2026).

As explained in the dedicated chapter on Living Labs, this methodology can entail a highly technical and scientific aspect. In fact, the GENESIS Living Lab in La Palma is intended as a real territorial laboratory integrating physical Nature-based Solutions, smart monitoring infrastructure, advanced numerical modelling and participatory governance mechanisms.

At the time of this deliverable writing, it is still not fully in place but preliminary steps were taken to ensure its quick establishment. To date, implementation has primarily advanced under preparatory activities related to permitting, inventories and mapping, analysis of island-level plans, selection and validation of NBS locations, preliminary studies and conceptual design. These activities have laid the technical and regulatory groundwork for the physical deployment of the four demonstrators. The next major step is the launch of construction activities. The Living Lab will function as a structured method for social engagement embedded within a real infrastructural transformation process.

Despite the fact that the analysis performed in this deliverable proved that Living Lab is not the most suitable methodology to deploy in La Palma, this does not preclude its development in the territory. On the contrary, it may still result in success and may provide further insights on how a methodology can be adjusted and performed despite theoretical sub-optimal conditions.

7. Conclusions

Public engagement and structured dialogue represent not only complementary components but foundational pillars for the successful mainstreaming of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in water governance across the Macaronesian region. The work carried out under Task 2.2 confirms that social legitimacy, institutional alignment, and long-term sustainability of NBS interventions depend substantially on the quality, inclusiveness, and contextual adaptability of participatory processes.

Building on the analytical framework developed in Deliverable D2.1, this document has translated diagnostic insights into operational guidance, identifying 11 participatory methodologies having different features. Indeed, the comparative analysis of participatory methodologies presented in this deliverable illustrates that no single engagement model is universally applicable. Instead, methodologies vary in their resource requirements, institutional demands, and capacity to generate actionable outputs. More sophisticated deliberative approaches - such as citizen juries, community visioning, deliberative workshops, and citizen forums - are particularly suitable in contexts characterised by moderate to high economic and institutional capacity and established traditions of civic engagement. Conversely, in territories facing resource constraints or lower levels of public awareness, lighter and more trust-building approaches - such as focus groups, world café formats, and creative participatory methods - may provide more appropriate entry points for strengthening dialogue and gradually reinforcing governance capacity.

Importantly, the “matching exercise” conducted should not be interpreted as prescriptive. Rather, it provides an ideal alignment framework, identifying enabling conditions under which specific methodologies are most likely to generate effective and legitimate outcomes. Local adaptation remains essential, and successful implementation depends less on the formal label of the method than on its contextualisation, facilitation quality, institutional anchoring, and follow-up mechanisms.

A recurring finding across both the literature review and practice-based insights from ALDA is that participatory processes generate both tangible and intangible outcomes. Beyond concrete recommendations or planning inputs, engagement mechanisms contribute to strengthening trust, improving inter-institutional coordination, enhancing transparency, and building long-term social capital. These intangible outcomes are particularly relevant in island contexts, where governance ecosystems are closely interconnected and where environmental vulnerabilities - especially concerning water scarcity and climate pressures - require collective and sustained responses.

In the specific context of the GENESIS project, public engagement serves a dual purpose. First, it enhances the social robustness and contextual relevance of NBS design and implementation. Second, it contributes to strengthening long-term water governance capacity across the Macaronesian archipelagos by fostering dialogue between citizens, experts, public authorities, and policymakers. By combining analytical evidence, methodological screening, and site-specific adaptation, this deliverable provides a structured framework to guide participatory strategies across the nine pilot territories.

Ultimately, the success of Nature-Based Solutions in the Macaronesian region will depend not only on technical performance but also on the ability of institutions and communities

to co-create, deliberate, and collectively assume ownership of water governance pathways. The participatory approaches outlined in this document represent practical instruments to support this transition toward more inclusive, resilient, and socially embedded environmental governance models able to transform the insights of such participatory approaches into actionable outputs.

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D.2.2 Guidelines for Public Engagement and Dialogue: Annexes

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Annex 1. Maderia Citizen Assembly Agenda Original document in Portuguese and Translated document in English

AGENDA DA SESSÃO PÚBLICA
- PROJETO GENESIS

Funchal, 7 de Outubro de 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101157447

**Funded by
the European Union**

Abertura (15 minutos) - 14h30-14h45

- Boas-vindas e apresentação da equipa organizadora (UMA, IGME, ALDA, EFG)
- Objectivos da sessão e panorâmica geral da agenda
- Regras de participação: diálogo cortês, valorização de perspectivas diversas
- Breve apresentação dos participantes (nome e função/ligação às questões hídricas locais)

Parte 1: Apresentação do Projeto GENESIS (15 minutos) - 14h45-15h00 (Alejandro)

- O que é o projecto GENESIS?
Objectivos e âmbito
- Explicação de soluções baseadas na natureza em linguagem acessível
- Cronograma do projecto e milestones
- Resultados esperados a nível regional (Macaronésia) e europeu

Parte 2: Impacto Local (30 minutos) - 15h00-15h30

- O que é o projecto GENESIS?
Objectivos e âmbito
- Explicação de soluções baseadas na natureza em linguagem acessível
- Cronograma do projecto e milestones
- Resultados esperados a nível regional

(Macaronésia) e europeu

Coffee break (15 minutos)_ 15h30-15h45

Parte 3: Diálogo com a Comunidade - 15h45-17h00

- Mesa Redonda (45 minutos) - 15h45-16h30
- Sessão Aberta de Perguntas e Respostas (30 minutos) - 16h30-17h00

Encerramento (15 minutos) - 17h00-17h15

- Síntese dos principais pontos discutidos
- Como o contributo da comunidade será utilizado
- Informações de contacto e oportunidades de participação contínua
- Agradecimentos e anúncio de próximas sessões

QUESTÕES PARA MESA REDONDA (questões propostas, provavelmente para reduzir ou passar para colaboradores na audiência)

TEMA 1: Desafios hídricos locais (15 minutos)

Na vossa perspectiva institucional, quais são os desafios mais críticos que a Madeira enfrenta na gestão dos recursos hídricos?
Que pressões existem sobre os sistemas actuais?

Como caracteriza o impacto das variações sazonais - entre períodos de precipitação intensa e de estiagem - na capacidade de resposta dos serviços públicos e na segurança das populações?

De que forma estes desafios hídricos condicionam sectores estratégicos como a agricultura, o turismo e o desenvolvimento económico regional? Existem análises de custo-benefício sobre os impactos actuais?

Face a estes desafios, que lacunas identifica nas políticas ou infra-estruturas existentes que projectos como o GENESIS poderiam ajudar a colmatar?

TEMA 2: Avaliação de soluções (15 minutos)

Qual a sua avaliação técnica/política sobre a solução de bacia de retenção/infiltração proposta para a Madeira? Como se alinha com as estratégias regionais de adaptação climática e gestão hídrica?"

Que sinergias identifica entre esta solução baseada na natureza e os planos sectoriais em curso - ordenamento do território, protecção civil, desenvolvimento rural?

Como perspectiva a integração da bacia de retenção/infiltração com as infra-estruturas existentes de drenagem pluvial e sistemas de protecção contra a erosão? Que desafios técnicos ou administrativos antecipam?

TEMA 3: Considerações sobre a Implementação (15 min)

Na sua opinião, qual deveria ser o modelo de governação para a manutenção e gestão a longo prazo desta infra-estrutura? Que entidades públicas ou privadas deveriam estar envolvidas?

Que condições institucionais, financeiras ou técnicas considera essenciais para garantir a sustentabilidade desta intervenção após o término do financiamento europeu?"?"

Que oportunidades de inovação tecnológica ou social identifica neste projecto? Como pode contribuir para posicionar a Madeira como referência em gestão sustentável

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Obrigado!

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**PUBLIC
AGENDA
PROJECT** - **SESSION
GENESIS**

Funchal, 7 October 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101157447

**Funded by
the European Union**

Opening (15 minutes) - 2:30 p.m. to 2:45 p.m.

- Welcome and introduction of the organising team (UMA, IGME, ALDA, EFG)
- Session objectives and overview of the agenda
- Rules of participation: courteous dialogue, valuing diverse perspectives
- Brief introduction of participants (name and role/connection to local water issues)

Part 1: Presentation of the GENESIS Project (15 minutes) - 2:45-3:00 p.m. (Alejandro)

- The what is the GENESIS GENESIS project? Objectives and scope
- Explanation of solutions based in nature in accessible language
- Project timeline and milestones
- Expected results at regional (Macaronesia) and European level

Part 2: Impact Local (30 minutes) - 3:00 p.m. to 3:30 p.m.

- The what is the GENESIS
GENESIS project? Objectives and
scope
- Explanation of solutions
based in nature in
accessible language
- Project timeline and milestones
- Expected results at regional
(Macaronesia) and European level

Coffee break (15 minutos)- 15h30-15h45

Part 3: Dialogue with the Community - 3:45 p.m. to 5 p.m.

- Round Table (45 minutes) - 3:45-4:30 p.m.
- Session Open from Questions and Answers (30 minutes) - 4:30 p.m. to **5:00 p.m.**

Closing (15 minutes) - 5:00 p.m. to 5:15 p.m.

- Summary of the main points discussed
- How the community's contribution will be used
- Information contact contact **and opportunities for ongoing participation**
- Acknowledgements and announcement of upcoming sessions

ROUND TABLE QUESTIONS (proposed questions, probably to be shortened or passed on to collaborators in the audience)

TOPIC 1: Local water challenges (15 minutes)

From your institutional perspective, what are the most critical challenges facing Madeira in water resource management? What pressures exist on current systems? How would you characterise the impact of seasonal variations - between periods of heavy rainfall and drought - on the capacity to response of public services and the safety of populations?

How do these water challenges affect strategic sectors such as agriculture, tourism and regional economic development? Are there any cost- benefit analyses of the current impacts?

In light of these challenges, what gaps do you identify in existing policies or infrastructure that projects such as GENESIS could help to fill?

TOPIC 2: Evaluation of solutions (15 minutes)

What is your technical/political assessment of the retention/infiltration basin solution proposed for Madeira? How does it align with regional climate adaptation and water management strategies?

What synergies do you identify between this nature-based solution and ongoing sectoral plans

- land use planning, civil protection, rural development?

How do you envisage integrating the retention/infiltration basin with existing storm drainage infrastructure and erosion protection systems? What technical or administrative challenges do you anticipate?

TOPIC 3: Considerations on Implementation (15 min)

In your opinion, what should be the governance model for the long-term maintenance and management of this infrastructure? Which public or private entities should be involved?

What institutional, financial or technical conditions do you consider essential to ensure the sustainability of this intervention after the end of European funding?

What opportunities for technological or social innovation do you see in this project? How can it contribute to positioning Madeira as reference in sustainable management

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Thank you!

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Annex 2. Maderia Citizen Assembly event report

Event Overview

The activity's design was based on ALDA's Citizen Assembly guidelines and aligned with GENESIS's goal of enhancing the climate resilience of water infrastructure and promoting civic engagement. UMa adopted an autonomous, revised approach. Funchal was selected for its accessibility to regional authorities and citizens, with the University providing a neutral, legitimate venue. It was decided to conduct the activity concurrently with the GENESIS Consortium annual meeting to take advantage of the presence of the project partners. Due to organisational constraints and limited participation (approximately 20 attendees), the planned Citizens Assembly was converted into a one-hour panel discussion, followed by a stakeholder roundtable and an open Q&A session.

Table 1. Overview of the citizen assembly organised in Madeira

Event detail	Description
Title	Citizen Assembly
Date	7 th October 2025
Duration	2 hours
Language	Portuguese
Location	University of MADERIA, R. dos Ferreiros Estrada, São Martinho, 9000-082 Funchal, Portugal
Target audience	40 (target) diverse stakeholders; General public, community leaders, local businesses, water stakeholders
Organiser	UMa

Objectives

The objectives of the Madeira (Portugal) Citizens Assembly (or panel discussion, as implemented) were based on the GENESIS project's key goals, which are to:

- Enhance the climate resilience of critical water infrastructures by shoring up support for NBS and the Genesis project.

- Combine civic engagement with innovation and science.
- To increase transparency and understanding of the Genesis project and the demonstrator site on Maderia.

Event Attendance

Total attendance did not meet expectations. The event saw the attendance of **approximately 20 participants**, many of whom represented GENESIS project partners, water management and environmental experts, and representatives of academic and research institutions.

Agenda

The event followed a structured agenda, which had been developed through contact between ALDA and UMA, found in Annex 2. This agenda was circulated on social media while advertising the event. Annex 3, translated into English, has also been attached.

Table 2. Preliminary agenda utilised for advertising event, translated from the original Portuguese, in Annex 2

Time	Duration (mins)	Activity
14:30	15	Opening session: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and introduction of the organising team (UMA, IGME, ALDA, EFG) • Session objectives and overview of the agenda • Rules of participation: courteous dialogue, appreciation of diverse perspectives • Brief introduction of participants (name and role/connection to local water issues)
14:45	45	Genesis project introduction presentation, given by Vitor Correia (EFG): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the GENESIS project? • Objectives and scope • Explanation of nature-based solutions in accessible language • Project timeline and milestones • Expected results at regional (Macaronesia) and European level

15:00	30	<p>Maderia's Demonstrator site presentation by Eduardo Leite (Uma)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of the need for the NBS Demo site • Explanation of how the NBS site will function • Expected results of the NBS being proposed
15:30	15	Coffee break
15:45	45	<p>Round Table</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic 1: Local water challenges (15 minutes) • Topic 2: Evaluation of solutions (15 minutes) • Topic 3: Considerations on Implementation (15 min)
16:30	30	Open Question and Answer Session
17:00	15	<p>Conclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How community input will be used • Contact information and opportunities for ongoing participation • Acknowledgements and announcement of upcoming sessions

Implementation

The expected number for a Citizen Assembly is significantly higher than 20 attendees; consequently, the team decided to convert the event into a panel discussion. The stakeholders panel proved to be interesting and insightful to the participants. Consisting of a few main components:

- Project Introduction and Discussion: The GENESIS project was introduced and discussed.
- 1-hour panel discussion: Included in the first day of the GENESIS Consortium General Assembly.
- Stakeholder Roundtable
- Open Q&A session

The stakeholders panel proved to be an engaging activity, but it represented limited knowledge exchange and societal engagement due to the homogeneity of the attendees.

Conclusion

The event was gender-balanced but was not fully inclusive (e.g., no language interpreters were foreseen), and the attendance lacked representation of residents outside of academia and civil service. The failure to gain enough attention to this event among citizens of Maderia will be further analysed and detailed in Deliverable 2.2.

Deliverable 2.2 will provide an analysis of the dialogue raised at the Citizen Assembly, which will be essential to incorporating insights gathered during this event into the Genesis Citizen Science Hub.

Annex 3. La Palma Citizen Water Forum Agenda **Original document in Spanish and translated** **document in English**

Foro Ciudadano del Agua

29 de Noviembre

09:00h - 14:00h

**Museo Arqueológico
Benahoarita (MAB)**

**Los Llanos de Aridane
La Palma, Islas Canarias**

Escanea el QR
para inscribirte

Financiado por
la Unión Europea

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del Programa de
Investigación e Innovación Horizonte Europa de la Unión
Europea en virtud del acuerdo de subvención Nº 101157447

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Foro Ciudadano del Agua

Los Llanos de Aridane, La Palma

Agenda

Sábado 29 de Noviembre

09:00- Recepción, registro y café de bienvenida

09:30- Apertura de la sesión

Gara Sentís y Alba Perera (Lawarita S.Coop.Can.)

10:00- Cómo predecir el futuro del agua en La Palma y Macaronesia

Alejandro García (IGME-CSIC)

10:30- Soluciones resilientes en acción: demostradores para el futuro del agua en La Palma

Iván Hernández (AIM)

11:15 - Presentación de grupos de trabajo

1:30 - Descanso y desayuno

12:00 - Dinámica participativa

Debate participativo

13:30 - Plenario

Conclusiones y cierre

14:00 - Almuerzo

ESCANEA EL QR PARA
INSCRIBIRTE

Citizens' Water Forum

November 29th

9:00 a.m. - 2:00 p.m.

Benahorita Archaeological
Museum (MAB)

Los Llanos de Aridane

La Palma, Canary Islands

Scan the QR Code
to register

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation
Programme under grant agreement No. 101157447

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Citizens' Water Forum

Los Llanos de Aridane, La Palma

Agenda

Saturday, 29 November

**09:00 - Reception, registration and
welcome coffee**

09:30 - Opening of the session
Gara Sentís and Alba Perera (Lawarita S.Coop.Can.)

**10:00 - How to predict the
future of water in La
Palma and Macaronesia**
Alejandro García (IGME-CSIC)

**10:30 -Resilient solutions in action:
demonstrators for the future of
water in La Palma**
Iván Hernández (AIM)

**11:15 - Presentation of
working groups**

11:30 - Break and breakfast

12:00 - Participatory dynamics
Participatory debate

13:30 - Plenary session
Conclusions and closing

14:00 - Lunch

Scan the QR
Code to register

Annex 4. La Palma citizen Water Forum event report

Event Overview

The La Palma Genesis Citizens Water Forum on Nature-based Solutions (NBS) was held on November 29th 2025, at the Archaeological Museum Benahoarita. Through this event, we aimed to engage diverse participants, including water experts and local residents. The event was structured in two parts: an explanatory morning session, which became a fairly dynamic debate due to engaging questions from the audience. Followed by a collaborative, interactive afternoon focused on small-group discussions regarding three core topics: Climate Change, Digitisation, and Decision-making and management.

Table 3. Overview of the La Palma Citizen Water Forum event

Event detail	Description
Title	Citizen Water Forum
Date	29 th November 2025
Duration	5 hours
Language	Spanish (with sign language and English interpretation)
Location	Archaeological museum Benahoarita, C. las Adelfas, 38760 Los Llanos, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Spain
Target audience	90 (target) diverse stakeholders; General public, community leaders, local businesses, water stakeholders
Organiser	Iván Hernández Ríos

Objectives

The primary objectives of the event were as follows:

- To promote local democracy, gather citizen input, and engage local citizens in water management.
- To increase transparency and understanding of the Genesis project on La Palma

- To identify key community concerns and priorities to be considered in WP2 and WP4
- To establish a long-term presence for citizen involvement in La Palma water management

Event Attendance

Total attendance exceeded expectations, with an estimated 66 participants registered. The demographic breakdown of attendees will be further analysed and detailed in Deliverable 2.2.

- Total Attendees: 66 people (36 men and 30 women).
- Audience: Participants were a mix of diverse stakeholders, including water-related experts, climate and environmental stakeholders, and a non-expert audience.
- Sectors Represented:
 - Public administration, the insular government authority
 - Private company environmental and water management consultancy
 - Civil society organisation, environmental association, non-profit
 - Agricultural sector association, private non-profit organisation
 - Civil society organisation focused on water management

The event followed a structured agenda, which had been developed through meetings of an advisory group and a preparation session for all GENESIS consortium colleagues who were assisting in the event. This agenda was circulated on social media while advertising the event.

Agenda

Table 4. Preliminary agenda utilised for the event, translated from the original Spanish, in Annex 5

Time	Duration (mins)	Activity
9:00	45	Registration
09:45	30	Opening: Facilitators welcomed and introduced the audience to the event agenda, objectives, format, and ground rules.

10:15	30	Explanatory session Presentation 1. Alejandro Garcia, IGME, presentation on the need for the Genesis project based on climate change risks. Followed by a Q&A session.
10:45	30	Explanatory Session Presentation 2. Ivan Hernandez, AIM, Presentation on the demonstrator NbS in La Palma and social engagement component. Followed by a Q&A session.
11:15	15	Introduction to the groups: The Facilitator allocated participants to each group and explained the goal of the discussion
11:30	30	Break
12:00	90	Group discussion: Groups discussed the three proposed topics (Climate change, Digitisation, and Decision-making and management).
13:30	30	Plenary Session: Each group presented the results of their discussions.
13:55	5	Conclusions, acknowledgements and last messages from the organisers.
14:00	-	Lunch offered to all participants

Explanatory session summary

Attendees registered and were welcomed by facilitators who introduced the event agenda, objectives, format, and ground rules. Consent forms for recordings and photography were distributed. The session began with an animated video commissioned by LRPC, which provided an engaging and simple overview of the deep demonstrator project on La Palma.

The animated video was followed by a presentation by The GENESIS Technical Project Leader, Alejandro Garcia, who presented on climate change risks across Macaronesia, why Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are a solution to mitigate the risk, and the Genesis project's expected results. A Q+A session followed this presentation.

The Q&A session following Alejandro's presentation focused primarily on data sharing, collaboration, the project's scope, and the definition of climate resilience. A major concern was the lack of calibration for the hydrogeological model, which was linked to data sharing restrictions and administrative barriers from public institutions.

The GENESIS WP4 partner leader/Activity leader from AIM then presented, which focused on the planned demonstrator sites across La Palma, its potential benefits, and the planned social engagement component of WP4. This was followed by a Q+A session. The Q&A session following Ivan Hernandez's presentation focused on the

reality of water reduction, data concerns, existing water issues, and the timeline for project benefits.

Group discussion summary

The session began with an introduction by consultants and an ALDA representative, framing the activity as an initiative to promote local democracy and ensuring participants that the results would be reported to the EU and made publicly available. Three groups of 10-12 citizens each were formed (Yellow, Blue, and Red), ensuring gender and age balance. A facilitator and a notetaker were assigned to each group. Project leaders and the General Manager of the La Palma Water Council were not present to avoid influencing the discussion.

The group work was divided into three 30-minute rounds to discuss three overarching topics: Climate change, Digitisation, and Decision-making and management. These three topics were pre-agreed by the advisory board to ensure the discussion remained relevant to the Genesis project, whilst not constraining the individuals to only discussing what they had learned of the project that day.

Participants were instructed to openly discuss the topic and to write their thoughts on post-it notes on the topic at hand, which were then placed on a poster and grouped into clusters by the facilitator based on similarity. Each round concluded with a voting moment where participants used stickers to express their preference for the most relevant cluster, which was equivalent to voting for the priority for each topic.

The yellow group discussion on climate change focused on practical solutions like irrigation improvements, promoting a water-saving culture, infrastructure renewal, forest protection, and reducing water-intensive crops. The yellow group discussion on digitisation stressed the need for technological solutions to be adapted to La Palma's specific context. Yellow group discussion on decision-Making focused on education and citizen awareness, alongside the need for improved public-private co-governance and updated regulations.

The Blue group discussion on Climate Change emphasised the urgency of reducing water consumption across sectors. Highlighted actions included education, awareness-raising, water reuse, rainwater harvesting, and maintenance of existing infrastructure. Blue group discussion on digitisation centred on sensors and remote (telematic) control. The debate focused on gaps in data collection, monitoring, transparency, and data-sharing, as well as concerns about equitable water accountability, particularly for farmers. Blue group discussion on decision-Making focused on governance models, the role of experts, transparency, and the balance of public/private responsibilities. They stressed the importance of independent studies, citizen participation, and accessible digital portals.

The red group discussion on Climate Change revealed four clusters of efficiency, storage, new water sources, and policy. Key discussion points included resistance to change, water storage challenges, and the perception of water as a public good. The red group discussion on digitisation focused on water consumption monitoring, data management, and participation. The debate emphasised the need for improved data collection, transparent sharing, and intelligent analysis, while raising concerns about

negative perceptions toward data provision, especially concerning farmers. The red group discussion on decision-Making led to two clusters: hydrological planning and citizen/technical participation. Participants called for reduced political influence, stronger expert involvement, and broader citizen engagement through transparent, accessible processes.

Plenary session

The group work was followed by a 30-minute plenary session, where representatives from each group volunteered to present their results to all attendees.

Water accessibility and governance were debated but central topic. The Yellow and Blue groups highlighted a strong need for more harmonious water co-management between public and private bodies, user communities, and owners of water infrastructures. All groups mentioned that the agricultural sector and/or farmers are disproportionately blamed for water use, emphasising that other sectors and economic actors should also be held accountable. All groups agreed on a lack of sufficient information and clarity regarding the use of water resources and citizens' consumption records, and noted the underutilization or misuse of data, particularly in policy-making. Further analysis of the plenary session results will be available on deliverable 2.2.

Conclusion

Learning from the previous Madeira event, the La Palma Citizens Water Forum proved to be a successful and productive exercise in citizen involvement, fostering a dynamic and collaborative atmosphere. The success can be attributed to robust preparation and the engaged community members who attended. All participants positively evaluated the activity and the collaborative atmosphere, expressing interest in more such participatory opportunities for improved democratic governance and understanding of water issues. Interviews were also conducted by VPCGT with both participants and members of the organisation team during the activity, allowing additional impressions of the experience to be gathered and acted on.

Deliverable 2.2 will provide an analysis of the dialogue and conclusions raised at the Citizen Water forum, which will be essential to incorporating insights gathered during this event into the Genesis Citizen Science Hub.

Annex 5. Notes of the Citizen Water Forum groups

Each of the groups was assigned a facilitator and note-taker. Below are the notes which were taken by the notetakers in the Group discussion session, which lasted approximately 2 hours. The notetakers were instructed to note the different ideas discussed, the clusters identified, the voting process for each of the topics.

Citizen water forum Yellow Group discussion notes

The Yellow Table consisted of 10 participants, of whom 3 were women and 7 were men. The discussion was conducted in a respectful manner, participants respected speaking turns and listened to each other, even when there were disagreements. Reaching consensus on how to group the post-it notes was initially challenging, once this was resolved the discussion progressed smoothly.

Adaptation to Climate Change

Idea Brainstorming

A total of 12 ideas emerged during the brainstorming session:

- Implementation of irrigation systems that maximise water efficiency.
- Reduction of water exports through crops and the search for alternative sources of income.
- Water resources should be publicly managed.
- Acceptance of current water scarcity conditions and rejection of denialism.
- Development of water reuse systems and promotion of a circular water cycle.
- Active promotion of water-saving practices by the Public Administration, including administrative support for storage systems and reduced water consumption.
- Improved use of runoff water.
- Creation of additional reservoirs.
- Public subsidies to repair and reactivate unused water tanks across the island.
- Readjustment of water distribution systems to prevent losses.
- Adaptation of existing infrastructure to improve efficiency.
- Implementation of controlled deforestation measures.

Discussion

The discussion was generally participatory and respectful, with most participants actively contributing to the exchange of ideas. Although one participant expressed scepticism regarding climate change, this did not prevent them from engaging in the activity, as they still contributed ideas by using post-it notes. Overall, differing viewpoints were expressed and discussed in a constructive manner.

Water-saving culture

A significant part of the discussion focused on the concept of a water-saving culture. Participants reflected on traditional water management practices in La Palma, noting that before the construction of galleries and wells, water was commonly collected in cisterns. In the context of today's highly dispersed administrative and social structure, it was suggested that these traditional techniques could be reintroduced or encouraged. Doing so could improve access to water, particularly for people living in more remote areas of the island.

Crop and economic model changes

Further discussion expanded on the cluster related to changes on crops and on the agricultural economic model. Participants noted that water is currently exported indirectly through agricultural production, particularly through banana cultivation, which is a water-intensive crop and has a significant water footprint. As most of this production is exported out of the island, some participants argued for the need to rethink the agricultural model, proposing a shift towards dryland crops or production aimed primarily at local or inter-island consumption.

Infrastructure maintenance and efficiency

The group also discussed infrastructure-related issues, emphasising that priority should be given to the repair, maintenance and optimisation of existing infrastructure rather than the construction of new facilities. It was pointed out that much of the current infrastructure shows signs of deterioration or abandonment, and that improving its efficiency could yield significant benefits.

Identified Clusters

There was considerable discussion regarding the organisation of ideas into thematic clusters. Due to the wide diversity of proposals, participants found it challenging to define clear titles and to group certain ideas under a single category. This process itself generated debate and reflection, highlighting the complexity of the issues addressed during the session. Finally, the ideas generated during the brainstorming session were subsequently grouped into 9 thematic clusters to facilitate analysis. These clusters reflect the main areas of concern and action identified by participants.

1. Improving irrigation

This cluster focused on the implementation of irrigation systems designed to maximise water efficiency.

2. Crop and economic model changes

This cluster addressed the need to reduce the export of water through agricultural products and to explore alternative sources of income.

3. Governance and management

This cluster highlights the importance of public management of water resources.

4. Truth or lie? Education

This cluster centred on the need to acknowledge the current reality of water scarcity and to reject denialism through education and awareness.

5. Reuse

This cluster included proposals for the development of water reuse systems and the promotion of a circular water cycle

6. Water-saving culture

This cluster emphasised the active promotion of water-saving practices by the Public Administration. This includes administrative support for the implementation of storage systems, and measures to reduce water consumption.

7. Improving water storage

This cluster brought together ideas related to a better use of runoff water, the creation of additional reservoirs and the provision of public subsidies to repair and reactivate unused water tanks across the island.

8. Efficient water capture and distribution

This cluster focused on the readjustment of water distribution systems to prevent losses and the adaptation of existing infrastructure to improve efficiency

9. Protection of forest mass

This cluster addressed the role of controlled deforestation as a measure to support sustainable water management.

Voting

The voting process was conducted in an orderly and respectful manner. Each participant had a clear idea of the cluster they wanted to vote. The clusters voted and the number of votes received was as follows:

- **Efficient water capture and distribution** (5 votes)
- **Water-saving culture** (4 votes)
- **Protection of forest mass** (1 vote)

Digitalisation

Idea Brainstorming

The following ideas emerged during the brainstorming session:

- Irrigation automation (two separate proposals)
- Adapt digitalisation processes to traditional practices, rather than replacing them
- Enclose channels in high-risk areas where they may become buried or inaccessible
- Doesn't consider digitalisation as something of primary importance
- Control the amount of water used in irrigation
- Remote reading of water levels
- Sensors in drainpipes
- Leak-detection systems
- Smart meters in households, particularly in hotels and tourist apartments

Discussion

The discussion was generally participatory and constructive, with most participants actively contributing their perspectives. While one participant expressed the view that digitalisation is not the key issue in water management and that other actions should take priority, the exchange of ideas remained respectful and focused.

Adapting digitalisation to local idiosyncrasies

Participants emphasised that digital tools imported to the island often do not align with La Palma's water culture. For example, irrigation techniques designed for flat terrain are being applied on the island's steep slopes. Similarly, equipment that functions well elsewhere may deteriorate quickly under strong sunlight. Participants argued that digitalisation must be adapted to the island's specific context, seeking a balance between traditional and digital methods to ensure both effectiveness and sustainability.

Automation systems and digital monitoring

The automation systems cluster generated multiple contributions, with four participants highlighting the value of digitalisation to understand water use and detect losses. These tools allow users to measure how much water is effectively lost compared to the amount paid for, providing critical data for management decisions. Automating irrigation or installing moisture control systems was also seen to prevent unnecessary water waste, for instance by avoiding irrigation when soil moisture is sufficient or reducing over-irrigation during wetter periods.

Complementarity of both ideas

Participants noted that adapting digitalisation to local idiosyncrasies and implementing automation systems are complementary strategies. They argued that mainland Spain often overlooks the unique context of the Canary Islands. They also emphasised that there is still time to align technology with the island's realities, ensuring that innovation can support rather than disrupt traditional water management practices.

Identified Clusters

The ideas generated during the brainstorming session were grouped into 6 thematic clusters

1. Irrigation automation

This cluster proposed implementing irrigation automation systems, including drip irrigation, to improve efficiency and reduce water wastage.

2. Adapting digitalisation to the island's idiosyncrasy

This cluster highlights the importance of adapting digitalisation processes to the islands' traditional practices, rather than imposing technology in a way that replaces or disrupts local techniques.

3. Modernisation

This cluster focused on improving infrastructure safety by enclosing channels in high-risk areas where they may become buried or inaccessible.

4. Not relevant

This cluster addressed the idea that digitalisation is not of primary importance, reflecting a difference in perspectives within the group.

5. Moisture control

This cluster included suggestions to monitor soil moisture to adjust irrigation according to the soil's needs.

6. Digitalisation – automation systems

This cluster grouped several ideas under the theme of digitalisation and automation for monitoring purposes. These included remote meter reading, sensors in drainpipes, leak-detection systems, and smart meters in households, especially in hotels and tourist apartments.

Voting

The voting process was conducted in an orderly and respectful manner. The participants voted 3 clusters:

- **Digitalisation - automation systems** (6 votes)
- **Adapting digitalisation to the island's idiosyncrasy** (3 votes)
- **Irrigation automation** (1 vote)

Decision-Making

Idea Brainstorming

A total of 11 ideas emerged during the brainstorming session:

- There should be an entity that oversees a control system managed by representatives of the water users
- In La Palma, water management is divided between public and private sectors; they should complement each other rather than work against one another
- Coordination among all stakeholders involved in water management
- Public–private co-governance of water
- Aid, subsidies, and reductions in property tax (IBI) for households that use water-storage systems such as cisterns or tanks
- Renewal and update of outdated statutes
- Creation of channels for citizen participation
- Incorporate the island’s history, culture, and the reality of water collection into education
- De-privatize resources
- Responsible and efficient water management
- Monitor the flow of galleries and wells at the beginning of the season, not only at peak flow

Discussion

The discussion was generally participatory and respectful, with participants sharing both personal experiences and technical perspectives. Ideas were debated thoughtfully, and differing viewpoints were addressed constructively.

Education and citizen action

Within the education cluster, participants emphasised the importance of incorporating Canarian history and water culture into schools. One participant noted that the history related to water is not sufficiently taught, while another participant, who was a teacher, highlighted that recent curricula now include Canary Islands history and geography, as well as heritage topics. These sometimes involve visits to water sources or ventilated galleries, such as the San Miguel Gallery.

Personal experiences were also shared to illustrate the historical significance of water management. One participant explained that their grandparents occasionally went hungry because they prioritised paying monthly gallery fees. Today, although galleries extend for 40 km, only about 20 km still provide water. It was really

dangerous mining those galleries. Participants stressed that the effort required to secure water historically is largely unknown to young people, and that education can foster citizen awareness and action to improve current water conditions.

Document renewal and governance

Regarding the renewal of documents, participants highlighted that outdated regulations fail to reflect the current reality of water availability. There is a widespread belief that water is abundant because of the outdated information, but the reality is quite different. Additionally, participants noted that water governance is influenced by the distribution of water shares, with those holding more shares having greater voting power. This concentration of influence can hinder necessary changes if those with the most power oppose reforms.

Identified Clusters

The ideas generated during the brainstorming session were grouped into 6 thematic clusters:

1. Public-private co-governance

Several proposals emphasised the need for stronger coordination between the public and private sectors. Suggestions included the creation of an entity to oversee water management with a monitoring system composed of representatives of water users. Participants also highlighted the importance of coordination among all stakeholders involved in water management, and that public and private stakeholders should complement each other rather than work in opposition.

2. Tax incentives

This cluster proposed the use of financial incentives to encourage the adoption of water-storage systems. These included tax incentives, subsidies, and reductions in property tax (IBI) for households using cisterns, tanks, or similar storage solutions.

3. Document renewal

This cluster suggested updating outdated legal and regulatory frameworks to ensure that water management statutes are current and effective.

4. Education and action

This cluster focused on citizen engagement and educational initiatives. Proposals included creating channels for citizen participation and incorporating the history, culture, and reality of water collection on the island into schools.

5. Deprivatization

This cluster saw deprivatization as a key measure to ensure equitable access and public control over water.

6. Responsible water management

This cluster emphasised that responsible and efficient water management practices, including monitoring the flow of galleries or wells at the beginning

of the season, rather than only during periods of maximum discharge, can optimise water use and detect potential issues early.

Voting

The participants finally voted for 2 clusters:

- **Education and action** (7 votes)
- **Public-private co-governance** (3 votes)

Final Conclusions

At the end of the exercise, participants reflected on the discussions and the voting outcomes. They found it was particularly interesting to note that, in both the climate change adaptation and decision-making discussions, the most voted clusters were related to education and culture. While improving water distribution and management remains important, participants emphasised that how citizens use water is equally crucial.

Across all three topics, participants ultimately voted for only two or three clusters, indicating a strong alignment in their concerns and priorities. This suggested that, despite the diversity of ideas, the group shared common perspectives on the most pressing issues.

Participants also highlighted the value of this type of collective discussion. Bringing together citizens from different backgrounds allowed for the exchange of ideas, active listening, and respectful debate. They noted that engaging in such a respectful environment can foster the emergence of new ideas, and if these debates also lead to tangible impact, it becomes even more beneficial for the community that takes part.

One participant noted that, although the initiative was very positive, she had only learned about it through a WhatsApp group. She highlighted the absence of farmers, a key sector in water management, and suggested that future events should be made more accessible. Publicity had largely been online, through channels that some farmers may not use, and many residents are older and may find digital forms challenging.

Citizen water forum Blue Group discussion notes

The Blue Group had 12 participants in total. One of the participants attended with his two teenage daughters, who mostly listened but occasionally contributed with some ideas. This is the main reason why in some topics the collected answers went from 10 to 11 participants. From the participants, in total there were 3 woman (+2 teenagers) and 7 men. The facilitator first introduced the session and explained the methodology for this whole session. The discussions were in some cases intense with disagreements on the topics, but they were carried respectfully and in most cases, it ended because we needed time to finish the session, so it did not end with a clear conclusion.

Adaptation to Climate Change

After reading the first theme, participants were given 5 minutes to write their ideas on post-its. Most participants finished in about one minute. A total of 11 contributions were collected:

- Promote the use of natural wastewater treatment
- Raise public awareness and counter far-right misinformation
- Climate change adaptation, reduction of water consumption, and improvement of water systems
- Maintenance of pipelines
- Water use through education
- Use of humidity through capture systems and smart irrigation technologies
- Saving water and avoiding waste
- Minimizing consumption
- Reservoirs and other water storage infrastructures
- Repair of gallery dams and traditional water channels
- Rainwater harvesting

Grouping of ideas

The facilitator explained the grouping method, and the following categories were formed:

- Public awareness
- Vertical and horizontal rainwater harvesting
- Promotion of water saving
- Maintenance of water transport infrastructures
- Reuse of water

Discussion

The debate on climate change was dynamic and highly collaborative, marked by a strong sense of shared concern about the island's vulnerability. Although participants came from different backgrounds (citizens, technicians, scientists), the conversation flowed with no confrontation. Instead, participants naturally built on each other's ideas, refining them until reaching a broad consensus.

Key points of the debate

• Strong emphasis on citizen education and awareness

Participants consistently stressed that behavioural change must start with education. Several highlighted that water-saving habits should be taught from childhood and reinforced through public campaigns.

They agreed that without societal awareness, any technical measure would have limited impact.

• Agreement on the urgency of reducing water consumption

The group recognised the need to minimise water use across all sectors and highlighted that climate change will amplify water scarcity, making preventive actions essential.

• Natural systems and nature-based approaches

There was particular interest in promoting natural water purification systems and rainwater harvesting, direct and indirectly. Participants saw these as low-cost, low-energy solutions aligned with sustainable adaptation.

• Maintenance of existing infrastructure

Several participants pointed out that climate adaptation also means ensuring that current systems work properly. Concerns included:

- aging pipes
- leaks in transport channels
- poor maintenance of gallery systems

These issues were viewed as a "silent loss" that undermines local resilience.

Throughout the debate, participants proposed multiple ways of grouping the ideas. They reorganised categories several times until everyone agreed on the final structure. This process showed active engagement and willingness to reach collective agreement.

Voting

At minute 25, participants voted for the most important groups.

The selected groups were:

- **Vertical and horizontal rainwater harvesting**
- **Awareness and promotion of water saving**

After reviewing the groups again, participants suggested merging some themes:

- Group 2 merged with Group 5 (rainwater harvesting + infrastructure maintenance)
- Group 3 merged with Group 6 (awareness + water saving), which became the second-most-voted option

Final agreed groups:

- Awareness and promotion of water saving
- Vertical and horizontal rainwater harvesting and maintenance of infrastructures
- Reuse of water

Digitalisation

When introducing the topic, some participants were unclear about mobile billing applications. It was clarified that the focus is on monitoring systems that allow users to control water use.

Participants proposed ideas quickly, within less than 5 minutes, except for two participants who took slightly longer. In total, 10 answers were collected.

Ideas collected

1. Digitalisation of resources and consumption
2. Pressure regulators (by flow) to maintain constant pressure
3. Sensors, meters, and digital applications
4. Reliable network of stations and soil moisture sensors
5. Sensorisation of networks for consumption control and leak detection
6. Use of flow meters (network and consumption control). For example, automatic shutoff during rainfall using telecontrolled valves
7. Pressure sensors in galleries for failure detection
8. Digital and automatic irrigation networks
9. Pipeline sensors for consumption, using low-cost regulating devices
10. Smart meters for households, irrigation systems, and administrations

Group formation

After reading the proposals, two broad groups were created:

1. **Sensors**
2. **Telematic (remote) control**

Discussion

This debate was highly participatory and sparked a wide diversity of perspectives. Unlike the climate change discussion, here opposing positions emerged, leading to a deeper exploration of needs and concerns, and a very active search for consensus.

Key points of the debate

- **Digitalisation as a key tool for data monitoring**

Participants emphasised that digital tools such as sensors, meters, humidity stations and remote-control systems, are essential for understanding how, where, and when water is being used.

They stressed the need to eliminate the negative connotations often associated with data sharing, clarifying that monitoring is not about surveillance but about transparent and efficient management.

- **Lack of clear data on water use**

A major concern was the current difficulty in knowing:

- how much water is consumed,
- its real allocation (agriculture, households, other uses),
- and its final destination.

Participants viewed this lack of clarity as a serious barrier to effective water planning.

- **Underutilisation of collected data**

Some participants stated that even when data are collected, they are not analysed, interpreted, or used properly. The group agreed that the key challenge is not only gathering information but ensuring that data leads to meaningful decisions.

- **Perceptions of responsibility and fairness**

A significant moment of debate emerged around the perception that farmers are frequently blamed for excessive water use. Participants argued that this view is oversimplified, noting that:

- domestic consumption is also highly relevant,
- losses in supply networks play a major role,
- and some sectors lack transparency.

This led to a broader reflection on equitable water accountability.

- **Need for shared, centralised data**

Participants pointed out that irrigation communities often hold the most valuable data but that sharing comes with a cost, not all members accept that cost, so data is therefore fragmented. By that, they emphasized that sharing data is time consuming and not everyone is willing to spend time sharing their data for free, or sometimes with costs related to the analysis of that data, so it is fragmented in terms that since it is not mandatory, the information is limited and given only by those willing to assume that responsibility. As this discussion emerged, they also mentioned that there are systems that share data automatically as a solution, but didn't go further in that topic

A unified system was seen as essential, but not yet feasible without structured incentives and administrative support.

- **Investment challenges**

There was consensus that:

- public administrations invest too little in upgrading supply chains,
- private water supply chains must justify investments economically and give transparency,
- and leakages cause significant losses that digitalisation could help detect (specially for private supply chains, where they need rentability).

Voting

Only two clear thematic groups emerged, *Sensors* and *Telematic control*, as participants felt these categories covered all proposals.

As only two groups were formed, these two were both discussed and given both the same importance.

Decision-Making

In about 2 minutes, 7 ideas were collected; by the end of the allotted time, a total of **10 proposals** were gathered:

1. Preliminary studies to identify essential investments
2. Management by user communities
3. Management by property owners
4. Water must be a public good, not a private one
5. Decision-making by professional experts
6. Citizen participation and community spaces
7. Management policies including farmers and local communities
8. Digital portals with updated data and real information sources
9. Education
10. Democratic user entities

Discussion and grouping

The debate on decision-making was the most politically and socially sensitive, as it touched on governance, ownership, and responsibilities. Several strong opinions were expressed, especially regarding landowners, user communities, and the role of experts.

Despite differing views, the discussion remained constructive and respectful.

Key points of the debate

• Need for preliminary studies before investments

Participants agreed that decisions should be based on updated, independent, and transparent studies. Some noted that investments are often made without a clear understanding of real needs.

• Management by user communities vs. Landowners

A significant debate emerged between those who supported decision-making by user communities and those who believed landowners (particularly owners of water infrastructures) should retain a decisive role. This debate revealed different perspectives on property rights, community participation, and the balance of power in water governance, without a change in the opinions that supported each side. It had to be ended as it was taking much time from the debate, making a stop to move on with other topics.

• **Water as a public good**

Several participants insisted that water should remain a public good, not a private commodity, especially in a context of scarcity. Others argued that private management systems have experience and knowledge that should not be disregarded.

• **Role of experts vs. Citizens**

The group recognised the value of expert-led decisions, especially for technical matters. But they also emphasised the importance of citizen participation, transparency, and democratic structures, while questioning who are really the “experts”, highlighting the need to clear this role and their study background/experience.

This led to discussions about how to combine expert knowledge, citizen involvement, fairness in governance

• **Transparency and access to real data**

Participants repeatedly highlighted the need for digital portals with updated, reliable information available to all. They agreed that transparency reduces suspicion, reinforces trust, and supports shared decision-making.

• **The need for a governance model shift**

Some participants argued that the island needs a change of model to adapt to new challenges.

Final grouping

After discussion, proposals 2 (expert-led decisions) and 4 (more studies) were merged, resulting in the most-voted group. Initial grouping attempts included:

- User-based management (tie)
- Expert-led decisions
- Transparency
- More studies
- Change of governance model (tie)

Voting

The most voted group was Expert-led decisions and more studies, followed by two more that remained tied.

Final Conclusions

To conclude the session, participants selected a spokesperson who would present the group's conclusions during the plenary exchange. The facilitator provided a brief explanation of the final task, outlining the structure for the presentation and the key points to highlight. The instructions were understood quickly and without difficulty.

Participants used the last moments to review their final groupings, ensure consensus on the selected priorities, and clarify the main messages they wished to convey. Despite the intensity of certain debates, particularly within the decision-making theme, the group demonstrated a constructive attitude, successfully transitioning from discussion to synthesis.

Citizen water forum Red Group discussion notes

A total of 12 citizens participated in this activity in the Blue Group, 5 women and 7 men. All of them participated in one way or another, contributing opinions in brainstorming sessions, debating the ideas presented and voting on what they considered to be the most relevant blocks in each topic. The overall atmosphere of the session was open and collaborative. Participants interacted respectfully, allowing space for different viewpoints, maintaining an orderly flow of interventions and demonstrating a willingness to listen and reflect on others' contributions. This constructive dynamic supported a productive and well-balanced discussion throughout the activity.

Adaptation to Climate Change

Idea Brainstorming

During the brainstorming session, the following proposals emerged:

1. Implement soil sensors and warning stations to improve water control and management.
2. Rationalise water use, promoting more efficient consumption.
3. Take measures to identify and reduce water losses, both high and low quality.
4. Collect water using different collection systems.
5. Promote the collection of water from roofs as a complementary source.
6. Incorporate desalination into the water supply system.
7. Improve the supply system, including water collection and storage.
8. Develop effective systems to reduce water losses in the network.
9. Move towards a transition to crops that are less demanding in terms of water resources.

Discussion

During the debate, various aspects related to water management and its technical, social and political implications were addressed. The debate was participatory and constructive, with everyone in the group contributing at least once. Although some people participated more actively than others, the exchange was balanced and respectful, allowing the discussion to proceed smoothly.

Water storage

With regard to storage, one advantage highlighted was that water is a resource that can be stored, allowing reserves to be available in times of scarcity and improving the capacity to respond to situations of water shortage.

Governance and policy framework

From a political and governance perspective, the difficulty of changing the mindset of communities linked to water was highlighted, as in many cases they are resistant to adopting new proposals or measures. It was also noted that many of these communities are not covered by current regulations, which complicates their management and regulation.

Resistance to change

There was evidence of general resistance to change on the part of the population and various stakeholders, which negatively affects the implementation of measures related to efficiency, storage, and water resource management.

Water management and the role of companies

During the debate, criticism was levelled at private water companies. It was argued that water is a basic necessity and that equitable access must be guaranteed to the entire population, while respecting the consumption associated with each property.

Data and knowledge of the resource

The sharing of water data from galleries and wells was identified as an advantage, as this facilitates decision-making and allows for a better understanding of the actual state of the water resource.

Costs and responsible water use

It was also considered necessary for users to bear the costs of the water they consume, as a measure to encourage more responsible use and contribute to better regulation of the resource.

Access to water and geological constraints

Finally, some people pointed out that, in their view, there are no problems with access to water on the island in terms of distribution, as no one is deprived of this resource and there is a willingness to share it when necessary. However, it was noted that, due to the island's geology, access to water sources can be complex, especially in the case of galleries and wells.

Identified Clusters

The identification of thematic groups was carried out in an orderly and structured manner. Participants engaged in constructive debate, presenting well-founded arguments to explain why they considered certain topics to be more relevant. Since all of them were affected by the issue, the debate reflected diverse perspectives and personal experiences, which enriched the exchange. Despite these different points of view, the group reached agreement on the titles of the thematic groups with relative ease, demonstrating a high level of mutual understanding and shared priorities.

Based on the ideas discussed, the following **final thematic groups** were identified:

1. Water efficiency and responsible use

This group includes discussions related to the rational use of water, the need for users to bear the costs of consumption, and the general resistance to change that affects the implementation of efficiency measures.

2. Water efficiency and responsible use

This group includes discussions related to the rational use of water, the need for users to bear the costs of consumption, and the general resistance to change that affects the implementation of efficiency measures.

3. Water storage and supply capacity

This group covers ideas related to water storage as a key advantage for ensuring reserves during periods of scarcity, as well as its role in improving the system's response to water shortages.

4. Water governance, policy framework and role of stakeholders

This group brings together issues related to governance and policy, including difficulties in changing the mindset of water-related communities, gaps in current regulations, and criticisms of private water companies regarding equitable access to water.

5. Data availability and knowledge of water resources

This group includes the sharing of data from galleries and wells, highlighting its importance for decision-making and for improving the understanding of the real status of water resources.

6. Access to water and territorial/geological constraints

This group addresses perceptions of water access on the island, the willingness to share the resource, and the limitations imposed by geological conditions on accessing water sources such as galleries and wells.

To organise ideas more effectively and facilitate the voting process, the group agreed to group the identified topics into broader blocks. This approach helped to structure the debate and provided a clearer framework for setting priorities. As a result of this process, four distinct thematic blocks were defined.

- Block 1. Efficiency
- Block 2. Storage
- Block 3. New Water Sources
- Block 4. Policy

Voting

The voting process was conducted in a calm and collaborative atmosphere, with no tensions or disagreements among participants. Rather than a strict numerical vote count, the group reached a consensus on the most relevant thematic blocks.

The thematic groups selected by the red group as the most relevant for Topic 1 were:

1. **Block 1. Efficiency** (consensus reached – no formal vote count)
2. **Block 2. Storage** (consensus reached – no formal vote count)

Digitalisation

Idea Brainstorming

During the brainstorming session, the following proposals emerged:

1. Introduce digital water meters to improve monitoring of water consumption
2. Implement meters for agricultural and livestock water consumption.
3. Digitise the sectors with the highest water consumption, particularly domestic and agricultural uses.
4. Enable remote control of irrigation systems and integrate soil moisture sensors.
5. Improve digital management of water systems.
6. Install sensors in pipes to detect leaks in the distribution network.
7. Computerise the distribution and use of irrigation water to optimise consumption.
8. Create digital discussion forums to support information exchange and participation.
9. Deploy smart meters in households.
10. Develop systems that allow comparison between extracted water and consumed water.

Discussion

During the debate, a wide range of perspectives related to digitalisation and water management were discussed. The discussion was highly participatory, with a greater diversity of opinions than in other sessions, including opposing viewpoints. These differences encouraged an active and constructive search for consensus among participants.

Digitalisation and monitoring of water consumption

The importance of digitalisation for improving data monitoring was highlighted, particularly as a means to eliminate the negative perceptions currently associated with the provision of information by users. Digital tools were seen as key to increasing transparency and trust.

Data clarity and data management

A lack of clarity regarding the volume of water used, consumed and its final destination was identified as a significant drawback, limiting effective water management. Although water-related data is often shared, it was noted that it is not always properly managed or used, leading to underutilisation of available information.

Data analysis and decision-making

The group agreed that, while data collection is essential, the analysis and interpretation of data are even more critical, as they enable informed and evidence-based decision-making.

Perceptions of water use and sectoral responsibility

Concerns were raised about the perception that farmers are disproportionately blamed for water consumption. Participants stressed that other forms of consumption, particularly domestic water use, are also highly relevant and should be considered equally in discussions on water use and responsibility.

Identified Clusters

Based on the ideas generated during the brainstorming session and the subsequent discussion, the following **final thematic clusters** were identified. These clusters group together related concepts and challenges in order to structure the debate and support further analysis.

Monitoring of water consumption

This cluster includes proposals related to the use of digital and smart meters in domestic, agricultural and livestock sectors, as well as tools that allow comparison between extracted and consumed water. The focus of this group is on improving transparency, traceability and accuracy in water consumption data.

Data management and analysis

This cluster brings together ideas related to the collection, management, analysis and interpretation of water-related data. It includes discussions on the proper use of shared data, the need to transform raw data into actionable information, and the role of digital tools in supporting informed decision-making.

Participation and stakeholder engagement

This cluster covers proposals aimed at improving participation and communication among stakeholders, including digital discussion forums and mechanisms to reduce negative perceptions associated with data provision. It also reflects concerns related to fairness in the attribution of responsibility for water consumption across different sectors.

To organise ideas more effectively and facilitate the voting process, the group decided to repeat the same dynamic applied in the previous topic, grouping the identified ideas into broader thematic blocks. This approach helped to structure the debate in a more orderly manner and made the voting process clearer and more manageable. As a result of this process, four distinct thematic blocks were defined.

- Block 1. Monitoring water consumption
- Block 2. Data management
- Block 3. Participation

Voting

The voting process took place in a calm and collaborative atmosphere, with no tensions or conflicts among participants. Rather than a strict numerical vote count, the group reached a clear consensus on the most relevant thematic blocks.

The thematic groups selected by the red group as the most relevant for Topic 2 were:

- **Block 1. Monitoring water consumption** (*consensus reached – no formal vote count*)
- **Block 2. Data management** (*consensus reached – no formal vote count*)
Decision-Making

Decision-Making

Idea Brainstorming

During the brainstorming session, the following proposals emerged:

1. Strengthen investment planning in water management.
2. Improve hydrological planning and governance, understood as sound and coordinated management.
3. Promote citizen participation in decision-making processes.
4. Encourage participation in public debates on water-related issues.
5. Increase involvement in the Island Water Council (CIALP).
6. Develop information systems with sufficient anticipation to support planning.
7. Improve decision-making management processes.
8. Ensure water use and management are properly reflected in political programmes.
9. Reinforce the role of technical decision-making.
10. Reduce political influence and increase the role of specialised professionals.
11. Promote transparency through accessible and affordable data.
12. Place the future and management of water at the centre of political agendas.

Discussion

During the discussion, participants actively exchanged and contrasted opinions based on the ideas previously presented. The debate was dynamic and participatory, with a strong focus on the role of decision-making processes in water management. In particular, the importance of citizen participation and technical expertise was repeatedly highlighted.

Planning, governance and investment

Participants emphasised that investment planning requires an informed and technical perspective to ensure the efficient use of available resources. Adequate hydrological planning and governance were considered essential, understood as coordinated management based on objective and long-term criteria.

Citizen participation and deliberative spaces

The importance of citizen participation at all levels was strongly highlighted, not only as recipients of information but also as active agents in decision-making. Participation in public debates was viewed positively, as a mechanism to bring together different perspectives and enrich decisions. In this context, the need for greater involvement in the Island Water Council (CIALP) was emphasised.

Decision-making processes and technical criteria

The management of decision-making processes was discussed, stressing the need for clear, transparent and participatory procedures. Participants defended that technical decisions should prevail over short-term interests, proposing a reduction of political influence and an increased presence of specialised professionals.

Transparency and political relevance of water management

Transparency was identified as a key element, highlighting the importance of accessible and understandable data for all citizens. Finally, participants agreed that the future and management of water must occupy a central place in political programmes, given its strategic importance for the island.

Identified Clusters

Based on the brainstorming outcomes and the subsequent discussion, two final thematic clusters were identified. These clusters reflect the main areas of convergence within the group and capture the core priorities related to decision-making and water management.

Hydrological planning and governance

This cluster groups ideas related to long-term water planning, investment strategies and governance frameworks. It includes discussions on the need for coordinated management, early planning tools, information systems to support decision-making,

and the integration of water management objectives into political programmes. The cluster emphasises the importance of structured, forward-looking and technically informed governance.

Citizen and technical participation in decision-making

This cluster brings together proposals focused on strengthening participation mechanisms and increasing the role of technical expertise in decision-making processes. It covers citizen involvement in public debates, participation in institutional bodies such as the Island Water Council (CIALP), transparency through accessible data, and the need to balance political influence with professional and technical criteria. The cluster highlights participation as a key element for legitimacy, transparency and effective water governance.

No modifications to these clusters were made during the debate, as participants showed a clear consensus on both their relevance and scope.

For the final activity, the group followed the same structured approach used in the previous topics, organising the ideas into broader thematic blocks to ensure clarity and facilitate the voting process. This resulted in the definition of two thematic blocks reflecting the priorities identified by the participants.

- Block 1. Hydrological planning
- Block 2. Citizen and technical participation in decision-making

Voting

The voting process was conducted in a calm and constructive atmosphere. As the options had previously been narrowed down to two thematic blocks, both were selected.

- Block 1. Hydrological planning (consensus reached – no formal vote count)
- Block 2. Citizen and technical participation in decision-making (*9 votes*)

Most of votes were cast in favor of the block focused on citizen participation and technical involvement, reflecting its perceived priority among participants.

Final conclusions

The group expressed a positive overall assessment of the activity, highlighting its productive nature and the good participatory dynamics throughout the exercise. Participants emphasised the value of having more spaces for citizen participation, particularly in relation to water management and decision-making processes.

Special importance was given to citizen participation, which was recognised as a key element for improving governance, increasing transparency and strengthening

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collective responsibility in water-related decisions. The group showed a shared willingness to continue engaging in similar participatory processes in the future.

Annex 6. Photography

Contained in this annex are examples of the photography taken during the Citizen Water event in La Palma, which was used for both press releases and social media posts. Efforts were taken to exclude the faces of people who did not wish to be photographed.

Figure 1. Photo taken from the back of the Citizen Water Forum event during Ivàn Hernández's presentation regarding the Living Labs

Figure 2. Group discussion and clustering of the red group. This photo features a facilitator pointing to a Post-it note

Figure 3. Two citizens and one facilitator present their groups results during the plenary session

Figure 4. Two Genesis partners stood outside the MAB before the event started